

LEVERAGING LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS FOR AUTOMATED DIGITAL FORENSIC ANALYSIS

By

Mohammad Sadiq

Student ID: 2376193

Supervisor: Dr.-Ing. David Oswald

A dissertation submitted to the University of Birmingham
For the degree of MEng. Computer Science and Software Engineering
Word count: 11087

School of Computer Science
College of Engineering and Physical Sciences
University of Birmingham 2024-25

April 2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

I. ABSTRACT	4
II. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	5
III. LIST OF FIGURES	6
IV. LIST OF TABLES	7
V. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	8
1 INTRODUCTION	10
1.1 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT	10
1.2 OVERVIEW OF DIGITAL AND MOBILE FORENSICS	10
1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT	11
1.4 RESEARCH QUESTION AND OBJECTIVES	11
1.5 CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE STUDY	12
1.6 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT	13
2 LITERATURE REVIEW	14
2.1 THE ROLE OF AI IN DIGITAL FORENSICS	14
2.2 TEXT CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES IN FORENSIC APPLICATIONS	14
2.3 TEXT SUMMARISATION TECHNIQUES IN FORENSIC APPLICATIONS.....	15
2.4 EVALUATION METRICS FOR FORENSIC NLP TASKS	15
2.5 SUMMARY OF LITERATURE GAPS	16
3 METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION	18
3.1 OVERVIEW OF THE RESEARCH.....	18
3.2 TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGY STACK.....	18
3.3 COMPONENT-A: DATA CATEGORISATION	19
3.4 COMPONENT-B: DATA SUMMARISATION	23
4 RESULTS AND EVALUATION	30
4.1 OVERVIEW OF EVALUATION STRATEGY	30
4.2 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 1 – TIME EFFICIENCY	30
4.3 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 2A (DATA CATEGORISATION PERFORMANCE) ...	31
4.4 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 2B (DATA SUMMARISATION QUALITY)	33
4.5 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 3 (PERFORMANCE THRESHOLDS FOR LLMS IN DIGITAL FORENSICS).....	35
4.6 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 4 (COMPARATIVE METRIC ANALYSIS).....	38
4.7 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 5 (RISK MITIGATION AND FUTURE WORKS)	40
5 CONCLUSIONS	42
5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS	42

5.2	CONTRIBUTIONS AND NOVELTY	42
5.3	LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	42
5.4	FINAL REMARKS	43
6	BIBLIOGRAPHY	44
	APPENDIX A: Full List of Statistical Evaluation Metrics Considered	47
	APPENDIX B: Source Code and Reproducibility Repository.....	48
	APPENDIX C: Prompt Templates	49
	APPENDIX D: Metric Definitions and Formulas.....	53
	APPENDIX E: User Interface Snapshots	54

I. ABSTRACT

The exponential nature of digital evidence has escalated forensic investigations into more intricate and time-consuming processes. Traditional manual processes are usually marred by inconsistencies and scalability challenges. LLMs offer possible solutions to automating critical functions such as data classification and conversational summarisation. However, their use in forensic settings is fraught with urgent concerns of hallucination, factuality, and evidentiary reliability that must be handled with care and sensitivity.

This study evaluates the applicability of LLMs within Digital Forensics and Incident Response (DFIR) through a two-component framework. Component A integrates LLM-driven entity categorisation into Autopsy via a custom plugin, with evaluation based on statistical metrics including Precision, Recall, and MCC. Component B applies LLMs to summarise chat data extracted from Android device images, using semantic evaluation metrics such as BERTScore and G-Eval.

Results show that LLMs can significantly accelerate forensic workflows, achieving over 90% accuracy in classification and producing high-quality summaries with iterative refinement. However, performance varies by model scale, with $\geq 8B$ parameter models (e.g., Gemma2 9B) striking a balance between reliability and deployability. The study concludes that LLMs are most effective when deployed locally within hybrid AI-human frameworks, where automation supports, but does not replace, expert oversight.

Keywords: Digital Forensics, Large Language Models, DFIR, NLP, Entity Classification, Chat Summarisation, G-Eval, BERTScore, Autopsy, Hybrid AI-Human Model, Open-Source LLMs, RAG, Explainable AI

II. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I want to express my sincere gratitude to all those who have supported and contributed to completing this dissertation.

Firstly, I am deeply grateful to my supervisor, Dr.-Ing. David Oswald, for his expert guidance, valuable feedback, and continuous support throughout this research. His encouragement has been crucial to the completion of this work.

I also appreciate the School of Computer Science at the University of Birmingham for providing the necessary resources and academic environment for this research.

A special note of gratitude goes to my father, whose insights and conversations helped shape the vision and direction of this project.

Finally, I would like to express my heartfelt thanks to my family and friends for their unwavering support during my studies.

III. LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Title	Page No.
Figure 3.1	End-to-End Workflow for Component A – SMS Categorisation	
Figure 3.2	Communication between Autopsy, Flask API, and Ollama-hosted LLMs.	
Figure 3.3	SMS filtering – default (left) vs. NER-enhanced plugin (right)	
Figure 3.4	End-to-End Workflow for Component B – Chats & SMS Summarisation	
Figure 3.5	Chat Data Preprocessing Pipeline for Summarisation	
Figure 3.6	Autopsy view showing raw, ungrouped chat logs with minimal context.	
Figure 3.7	UI with AI-grouped chats, filterable by ID and type for forensic review.	
Figure 3.8	Chat Data Preprocessing Pipeline for Summarisation	
Figure 4.1	Accuracy and G-Eval Score Comparison for SMS Categorisation Models	
Figure 4.2	Visual comparison of summarisation quality using G-Eval and BERTScore across datasets	
Figure 4.3	MCC score comparison across models	

IV. LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title	Page No.
Table 1.1	Research Objectives and Expected Contributions	
Table 3.1	Technologies Used Across Components A and B	
Table 4.1	Comparison of Manual vs LLM-Assisted Task Completion Time	
Table 4.2	Key Evaluation Metrics for Forensic Categorisation Accuracy	
Table 4.3	Comparative Performance of LLMs in SMS Entity Categorisation	
Table 4.4	G-Eval and BERTScore performance across Android 7 and Android 12 datasets	
Table 4.5	List of models compared	
Table 4.6	Comparative performance of four LLMs (Gemma2 2B, Llama 8B, Gemma2 9B, GPT-4o)	
Table 4.7	Metrics considered for Component A	
Table 4.8	Metrics considered for Component B	
Table 4.9	Risk Identification, Observation, Mitigation, and Future Enhancements	

V. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATION	FULL FORM
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
BLEU	Bilingual Evaluation Understudy
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DFIR	Digital Forensics and Incident Response
G-Eval	Generative Evaluation Framework
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLM	Large Language Model
MCC	Matthews Correlation Coefficient
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NER	Named Entity Recognition
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
SMS	Short Message Service
UI	User Interface
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VPN	Virtual Private Network
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
ALEAPP	Android Logs and Protobuf Parser
SVM	Support Vector Machine
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ROUGE	Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation
GPT	Generative Pre-trained Transformer
REST	Representational State Transfer
UCI	University of California, Irvine
NUS	National University of Singapore

ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
SQL	Structured Query Language
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
ID	Identifier / Identification

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

The field of digital forensics is evolving rapidly due to the exponential rise in digital evidence and the widening application of mobile communication in both civilian and criminal activity. Examiners must now process vast volumes of unstructured text data, such as SMS, chat messages, and application logs, often with tight legal deadlines and minimal automation support. Forensic processes are mostly done manually, dependent upon keyword search, professional judgment, and painstaking case triage, contributing to elevated time utilisation, variability, and error potential.

The recent advancements in AI, particularly LLMs, open the possibility of a promising way forward. LLMs can perform higher-level natural language tasks such as entity recognition, summarisation, and classification, and have been successful across industries from healthcare to education and legal analytics. These capabilities render LLMs a strong candidate for reducing forensic workflow manual overhead and improving investigative accuracy (Quick and Choo, 2018)

Despite their promise, the adoption of LLMs in digital forensics remains limited. Many AI-enhanced forensic tools are proprietary, expensive, or designed for enterprise environments, rendering them inaccessible to independent analysts or smaller law enforcement units. Open-source tools, such as Autopsy, offer broad accessibility but lack native integration with LLMs or advanced AI models (Garfinkel, 2010). Moreover, concerns regarding data privacy, hallucinations, and the explainability of AI outputs further hinder mainstream adoption in forensic settings.

This study addresses these challenges by proposing an open-source, LLM-integrated forensic workflow. The goal is to make advanced AI capabilities more accessible, reliable, and aligned with forensic principles.

1.2 OVERVIEW OF DIGITAL AND MOBILE FORENSICS

The detection, collection, preservation, analysis, and documentation of digital evidence from electronic devices, including computers, smartphones, and cloud storage, are all part of DFIR. Mobile forensics has become a prominent subfield since mobile phones are now essential to contemporary communication, allowing investigators to retrieve and examine data, including transaction logs, SMS messages, application-based chats, and GPS locations.(Eoghan Casey, 2011).

Mobile forensics presents unique challenges due to the volume and complexity of data, which are unstructured, context-relevant, and disseminated over multiple applications. SMS and chat data must be interpreted, not keyword-matched, with semantic understanding, contextual packaging, and temporal correlation requirements.

Tools like Autopsy and ALEAPP are the standard in digital forensics for handling mobile artefacts today. Autopsy provides a forensic environment in a modular structure to examine disk images, while ALEAPP is typically utilised for log and app data extraction from Android devices. Both tools lack built-in AI capabilities to perform higher-level tasks such as entity classification, semantic labelling, or conversation summarisation. As a result, analysts continue to rely on manual filtering, which restricts consistency and scalability, particularly in high-volume investigations.

By providing structured, AI-based insights with little human involvement, incorporating NLP techniques, particularly those driven by LLMs, into these systems can potentially improve digital forensic processes.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The exponential growth in digital data poses a considerable challenge to modern forensic analysis. The UK's National Digital Forensic Science Strategy (NPCC, 2020), indicates that digital forensic case data volumes are expanding at approximately 11–16% annually, contributing to increasing case backlogs and extended investigation durations. As complexity in mobile and digital communications increases, so does the task for forensic examiners, who must analyse large quantities of text-heavy evidence, often with minimal automation support.

Sorting, categorising, and examining evidence by hand, such as chat logs and SMS, is a core component of old-school digital forensic work. These processes are labour-intensive and prone to mistakes; outcomes rely on the investigator's experience, tiredness, and judgment. Consistency can contaminate evidential traceability or delay justice by compromising the integrity and promptness of investigations.

While LLMs demonstrate capabilities for automating complex natural language tasks, their application in digital forensics is still nascent. Existing tools are either proprietary and costly or lack the forensic domain adaptation necessary to process evidential data accurately and accountably. These problems are associated with AI-related issues, namely hallucinations, lack of contextual grounding, and unexplainable behaviour, further discouraging safe deployment within forensic contexts.

This project aims to investigate whether integrating LLMs into open-source forensic workflows can reduce manual overhead, speed up and normalise the pace of digital investigations, and overcome challenges such as hallucination and misclassification of evidence while complying with privacy, legal, and operational constraints.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTION AND OBJECTIVES

The central research question is:

Can LLMs effectively and safely enhance digital forensic investigations by improving data categorisation and interpretation, reducing time inefficiencies, and mitigating risks such as hallucinations and misinterpretations?

To address this question, five research objectives were defined (Table 1.1), each targeting a distinct aspect of forensic-AI integration:

Table 1.1: Research Objectives and Expected Contributions

OBJECTIVE	FOCUS AREA	EXPECTED CONTRIBUTION
Objective 1	Time efficiency	Measure if LLMs can reduce manual workload and accelerate forensic workflows.
Objective 2	Classification and summarisation accuracy	Evaluate LLM performance on structured (SMS) and unstructured (chat) forensic tasks.
Objective 3	Model scale analysis	Identify the minimum LLM parameter size needed for forensic-grade reliability.
Objective 4	Evaluation methodologies	Assess the suitability of different statistical and model-based metrics in forensic AI validation.
Objective 5	Future enhancements	Propose practical enhancement pathways for forensic AI workflows by identifying challenges and recommending mitigations, as well as exploring advanced techniques that emerged during the project but were beyond the scope of the current implementation.

1.5 CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE STUDY

This research makes the following key contributions to the field of digital forensics and AI integration:

Integrated LLMs into Open-Source Forensic Tools

I developed a custom plugin for Autopsy, a widely used open-source forensic suite, to enable automated categorisation of SMS data using locally hosted LLMs. The plugin supports evidence tagging and semantic filtering, allowing investigators to streamline their analysis directly within the Autopsy environment.

Designed and Deployed a Standalone Summarisation Interface

I built a web-based interface that allows users to generate and explore LLM-generated summaries of chat conversations extracted from Android forensic images. The interface supports timeline views, custom filters, and expandable summaries, making large volumes of communication data easier to interpret.

Benchmarked LLMs Across Multiple Scales and Sources

I evaluated a range of LLMs on forensic classification and summarisation tasks, including Gemma2 2B, LLaMA 8B, Gemma2 9B, and GPT-4o. This benchmarking helped identify the minimum viable model scale for reliable forensic performance and assessed the trade-offs between open-source accessibility and proprietary model accuracy.

Implemented a Hybrid Evaluation Framework

I adopted and validated a hybrid evaluation strategy that combines statistical metrics (e.g., Precision, Recall, F1 Score, MCC) with semantic and LLM-based scorers (BERTScore, G-Eval). This framework provides a balanced and forensically aligned approach for validating LLM performance on structured and unstructured data.

Proposed Risk Mitigation and Future Enhancements

I addressed potential problems such as hallucination, bias, and forensic fidelity loss. I outlined methods for mitigating such issues through prompt engineering, iterative tuning with G-Eval, and later integration of RAG and XAI to promote system explainability and trustworthiness.

1.6 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

This report is organised into five main sections:

- **Section 2: Literature Review** – Surveys prior work in digital forensics and AI integration, identifies current gaps, and positions this study within the research landscape.
- **Section 3: Methodology and Implementation** – Describes the technical architecture, tools, and design of the Autopsy plugin and summarisation interface, including the LLM integration strategy.
- **Section 4: Results and Evaluation** – Presents experimental results across all research objectives using quantitative and semantic metrics, supported by visual analyses and comparative discussion.
- **Section 5: Conclusion** – Summarises key findings, outlines limitations, and proposes future research directions, including using RAG, model explainability, and automated reporting systems.
- **Appendices** – These contain detailed tables, sample outputs, evaluation scripts, and references to the GitHub repository for reproducibility.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THE ROLE OF AI IN DIGITAL FORENSICS

The changing nature of digital crime has demanded new adaptive forensic methods. Traditional forensic techniques usually depend on manual inspections, keyword searches, and signature-based artefact detection, approaches that, although useful, tend to become inefficient and prone to errors as evidence volumes grow.(Garfinkel, 2010). Consequently, AI, especially in areas such as NLP, is becoming more significant in automating forensic workflows.

AI-driven tools can process unstructured data (like SMS, emails, and chat logs) with contextual awareness. This makes tasks such as entity extraction, semantic classification, and anomaly detection. These features are crucial for uncovering relevant information hidden in large datasets and can greatly alleviate the cognitive load on forensic analysts. (Landauer et al., 2022; - et al., 2024; Iyengar et al., 2024).

Numerous AI-assisted forensic frameworks have been developed in the last decade. For example, models incorporating decision trees, SVM, and RNN classify message content and identify unusual communication.(Dr. Pankaj Malik et al., 2024). Lately, AI methods have been integrated into digital forensic process models, enriching traditional steps such as data acquisition, examination, and analysis through intelligent automation. (Dunsin et al., 2024).

While AI offers benefits, its application in digital forensics presents challenges. Critical concerns about reproducibility, explainability, and evidentiary integrity persist where AI-provided insights are used in court. Nevertheless, AI technologies are expected to contribute increasingly to investigation processes as forensic data becomes increasingly diverse.

2.2 TEXT CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES IN FORENSIC APPLICATIONS

Text classification is fundamental in digital forensics, particularly when dealing with unstructured or semi-structured communication data such as SMS, emails, and chat logs. In the forensic context, classification is often aimed at organising messages into categories such as threats, financial transactions, personal identifiers, or location references, which are critical elements during the triage and analysis stages.

Traditional classification methods, such as Naive Bayes, SVMs, and Decision Trees, have been widely used in earlier systems for text classification(Li et al., 2022). For instance, (Nwankwo et al., 2020) These techniques were applied to classify SMS messages extracted from mobile devices, demonstrating their utility in organising forensic evidence. However, they are limited in handling context and linguistic variation.

To overcome these limitations, modern approaches now integrate deep learning techniques. (Mr.N.Arikaran et al., 2024) proposed a three-tier forensic classification framework incorporating CNNs, RNNs, and Transformer-based architectures to extract features and classify evidence from diverse modalities, including text. These models automatically learn representations of text and have been shown to outperform traditional classifiers in multiple classification tasks (Minaee et al., 2020).

Parallel to the development of this project, interest in applying LLMs to digital forensics has been growing. (Yin et al., 2025) Recently, a framework was proposed that leverages LLMs for various forensic tasks, including multilingual analysis, evidence synthesis, and anomaly detection. Although

their work takes a broader perspective, it reflects similar ideas around using prompt-based language models for flexible text classification.

The emergence of such studies during this research highlights the increasing recognition of LLMs as a viable approach in forensic analysis.

2.3 TEXT SUMMARISATION TECHNIQUES IN FORENSIC APPLICATIONS

Summarisation plays a crucial role in digital forensics, particularly during the review of chat logs, emails, and other long-form communications. Investigators often need to rapidly understand the context and content of message threads without reading each message individually. Traditional summarisation techniques in digital forensics generally fall into two categories: **extractive** and **abstractive** (Automatic summarization - Wikipedia, n.d.)

Extractive Summarisation: This approach involves selecting key sentences directly from the original text, often based on keyword density or positional heuristics. For instance, (Alves et al., 2023) applied extractive techniques such as TF-IDF, RAKE, and TextRank to identify relevant information in high-volume chat logs associated with criminal investigations. Their study found that these traditional methods struggled with the informal language, abbreviations, and fragmented sentence structures commonly present in forensic communication data.

Abstractive Summarisation: In contrast, abstractive summarisation generates new sentences to paraphrase the content of the original conversation, requiring deeper language understanding. This technique is well-suited for forensic applications where conversations may include slang, indirect references, or fragmented dialogue. (Deroy et al., 2023) explored the application of pre-trained abstractive models and LLMs for summarising legal case judgments. Their study found that while these models can produce more natural and coherent summaries than extractive methods, they also present challenges such as inconsistencies and hallucinations, highlighting the need for careful evaluation in sensitive domains like legal and forensic contexts.

2.4 EVALUATION METRICS FOR FORENSIC NLP TASKS

Evaluating NLP tools in forensic contexts requires domain-related factors rather than a general-purpose assessment. General-purpose metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1 Score are necessarily rudimentary, particularly for structured data classification. Forensic analysis, however, typically deals with biased datasets and high-consequence conclusions, necessitating stronger and more advanced assessment methodologies.

One such measure is the MCC, which is commonly accepted as a balanced measure in binary and multi-class classification, even for skewed data distributions. MCC, as per (Chicco and Jurman, 2020) performs better than other measures when false positives or negatives are highly important. These are often present in forensic categorisation tasks like detecting sensitive entities (e.g., financial transactions, dates, or named entities).

For text summarisation, conventional overlap-based metrics such as ROUGE and BLEU are generally used for lexical similarity. However, these are inadequate for forensic NLP since they do not account for paraphrasing, semantic similarity, and hallucination sensitivity. Semantic assessment tools such as BERTScore (Zhang et al., 2019) and G-Eval (Liu et al., 2023) have become more suitable alternatives. BERTScore calculates the contextual similarity between generated and reference texts using pre-trained language embeddings, offering better alignment with human judgment in forensic review scenarios.

G-Eval uses GPT-4 to assess generated outputs across multiple dimensions such as coherence, fluency, consistency, and factuality. Unlike static metrics, G-Eval dynamically interprets input and output content, allowing it to better approximate human judgment in open-ended tasks like summarisation and explanation.

In this project, G-Eval was used to evaluate both entity classification and summarisation outputs through custom-designed prompts emulating the scrutiny of a forensic analyst. This approach aligns with emerging practices in the field. For example, (Sharma et al., 2025) Applied G-Eval in their evaluation of *Forensicllm*, a domain-specific language model fine-tuned on digital forensic literature. Their results showed that G-Eval scores closely matched expert evaluations across multiple categories, reinforcing the tool's utility in assessing the quality of LLM-generated forensic narratives.

This project adopted a hybrid evaluation strategy that reflects real-world forensic requirements by combining statistical, semantic, and model-based evaluations. This aligns with recent recommendations by (Sottana et al., 2023) , who advocate for multi-metric, context-sensitive validation methods in critical NLP applications.

2.5 SUMMARY OF LITERATURE GAPS

The literature on applying LLMs in digital forensics reveals several promising directions and highlights key limitations that this study aims to address.

First, while recent studies have explored AI techniques for forensic tasks, much of the existing research remains siloed, demonstrating proof-of-concept models without full integration into operational forensic workflows. For example, LLM's are often used in academic settings, but their application within widely used platforms such as Autopsy is still rare. This limits the real-world utility of forensic AI models, particularly in casework that requires domain-specific Categorisation and traceable evidence handling.

Second, although recent studies have started using semantic and model-based metrics, such as BERTScore and G-Eval, to evaluate forensic NLP outputs, no standardised evaluation pipeline is tailored to forensic needs. Existing approaches often use these metrics in isolation, without combining them into a cohesive framework that reflects forensic priorities like factual consistency, evidential traceability, or hallucination risk. In particular, hybrid strategies that blend statistical metrics, semantic similarity, and human-aligned model judgment are rarely formalised or validated in forensic contexts.

Third, while research has explored the use of open-source or locally hosted LLMs (e.g., LLaMA, Gemma) for forensic tasks, many user-facing applications and prototypes still rely on cloud-based APIS, particularly from providers like OpenAI, due to their ease of use and superior performance. However, forensic analysis involves sensitive, legally protected data, which often cannot be transferred to third-party servers. As a result, there is a critical need to develop workflows that support privacy-preserving, offline model deployment, enabling LLM-based capabilities without compromising case integrity or violating evidentiary standards.

Finally, while parallel studies have demonstrated the value of fine-tuned LLMs for forensic tasks, they typically focus on evaluating a single model size. This leaves the question of the minimum viable model size for achieving reliable forensic performance open. In real-world forensic environments, where models must often run locally on constrained hardware, balancing performance with latency, resource usage, and interpretability is essential. A systematic comparison across different model scales is therefore critical for guiding deployment decisions in practice.

In response to these gaps, I propose a practical framework that integrates LLMs into open-source forensic tools, adopts a hybrid evaluation pipeline, and systematically benchmarks models across scales. These efforts directly support the project's core contributions, as outlined in Section 1.5, and are designed to advance the practical, secure, and scalable application of LLMs in digital forensic investigations.

3 METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 OVERVIEW OF THE RESEARCH

I planned the research into two distinct components, Data Categorisation (Component A) and Data Summarisation (Component B), to address the varied nature of digital evidence encountered in forensic investigations. This division reflects the practical realities of forensic workflows, where investigators must analyse structured data (SMS messages) and unstructured data (chat logs from social media platforms).

To support this, I focused Component A on building an Autopsy plugin capable of classifying structured SMS data into forensic-relevant categories. In contrast, Component B targets unstructured conversation data, which I processed and summarised through a custom web interface to reduce cognitive load and highlight key information.

As discussed in the previous section, this study is driven by five key research objectives, evaluated through a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to ensure both accuracy and practical usability

3.2 TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGY STACK

To support seamless integration of LLMs within digital forensic workflows, I employed a combination of open-source forensic toolkits, local AI hosting frameworks, and communication middleware. The selection criteria prioritised open accessibility, compatibility with structured and unstructured data, and support for local inference to ensure forensic data security.

Table 3.1: Technologies Used Across Component A and B

A summary of the key tools and frameworks integrated in the project for forensic analysis, local model hosting, data extraction, and visualisation.

COMPONENT	TECHNOLOGIES USED	PURPOSE
A & B	Ollama (Gemma 2 9B, Llama 3,8 B GPT-4o)	Hosting local LLMs for on-device inference
A & B	Flask (Python)	RESTful server for LLM communication
A	Autopsy (Java + Jython)	Primary forensic platform with plugin extensibility
A	jdk.httpserver	Java HTTP server to interface with external Python logic
A & B	SQLite	Database querying for SMS data
B	ALEAPP	Android log extraction from mobile images
B	HTML/CSS/JavaScript	UI for visualising summaries and chat reconstruction

This modular stack enabled scalable AI workflows, kept forensic data locally processed, and preserved compatibility with industry tools like Autopsy and ALEAPP.

3.3 COMPONENT-A: DATA CATEGORISATION

3.3.1 Architecture and Integration Design

Autopsy is an open-source forensic platform written in Java. It provides a modular interface for forensic data ingestion, analysis, and evidence tagging (Brian Carrier, 2000; Autopsy (software) - Wikipedia, 2025). To integrate LLM-based text classification into this environment, I developed a Jython plugin, which enables Python code to operate within Autopsy's Java runtime.

However, Jython cannot access external Python libraries, such as requests or transformers, limiting its compatibility with NLP libraries and modern LLM frameworks. To overcome this, I embedded a Java HTTP server (via `jdk.httpserver`) within the plugin. This allowed Autopsy to send extracted forensic data to an external Python-based Flask server, which ran independently of Autopsy's internal environment.

The internal HTTP server accepted outbound JSON-formatted data from the plugin and forwarded it to the Flask API (`http://localhost:8000/reply`). This allowed the forensic plugin to offload Categorisation logic to a dedicated Python environment. The Flask server then relayed this input to an LLM hosted locally via Ollama, which performed the semantic Categorisation.

Categorised responses were routed back through the same HTTP server and converted into custom Autopsy artefacts, making the integration seamless for investigators working within the Autopsy GUI.

3.3.2 Implementation Workflow

The end-to-end implementation of Component A follows a six-stage architecture, illustrated in Figure 3.1 below. These stages represent the complete process from raw SMS ingestion to AI-assisted Categorisation, evaluation, and refinement within the Autopsy environment.

Figure 3.1: End-to-End Workflow for Component A – SMS Categorisation

Stage I – Dataset Collection

To support the forensic categorisation task in Component A, I designed a dataset curation methodology that emphasised both realism and relevance to forensic contexts. The objective was to simulate investigative scenarios where diverse, unstructured, and multilingual SMS communications are encountered. Publicly available ham (non-spam) datasets were chosen to reflect benign but semantically

rich content, avoiding noise from adversarial spam. Primary sources included the UCI SMS Spam Collection, NUS, and Indian SMS Spam Collection. These corpora were selected based on their coverage of real-world messaging patterns, linguistic diversity, and availability of structured labels.

In total, I aggregated approximately 175,000 SMS messages across the sources. To address computational constraints and avoid data imbalance, I developed a custom Python script to clean, filter, and reduce the dataset to a curated subset of 5,000 messages. The script removed malformed entries, non-ASCII text, and duplicates, then applied stratified random sampling to preserve thematic and linguistic diversity. To further enhance authenticity, I augmented the corpus with personal SMS messages from my device, covering a two-year period. The resulting dataset was used for LLM-based categorisation and evaluation in subsequent stages.

Stage II – Data Ingestion

I structured the ingestion process around a mobile-compatible database format to prepare the SMS dataset for forensic analysis. The aim was to replicate the typical schema used in Android devices for storing SMS data, ensuring compatibility with Autopsy's internal parsing mechanisms. This allowed the dataset to be treated like a native forensic artefact, maintaining structural integrity during plugin-based analysis.

Using a custom script, I converted each SMS message into an SQL INSERT statement and populated a SQLite database named `mmssms.db`, which mirrors the standard Android SMS schema. When the plugin, developed in Jython, is executed within Autopsy, it automatically locates this database, extracts message content, and serialises it into JSON format. This structured JSON payload is sent to the external AI processing layer for LLM-based categorisation.

Stage III – LLM Communication & Data Categorisation

To enable automated semantic analysis of forensic SMS data, I implemented an integration workflow that transmits each extracted message to a locally hosted Flask API. This API bridges Autopsy's Java environment and the Python-based LLM processing layer.

Models such as Gemma2 2B, Gemma2 9B, and LLaMA 3B/8B were deployed locally using Ollama, while GPT-4o was utilised through the OpenAI API for benchmarking.

These models were hosted either on the local machine or a remote GPU server within the university network, accessed securely via a VPN tunnel. This setup ensured low-latency inference while preserving data privacy.

Figure 3.2 illustrates the overall architecture, depicting how Autopsy, Flask, and the remote LLM inference server were interconnected through IP-based routing and VPN tunnelling to maintain secure and isolated processing within the forensic environment.

Figure 3.2: Network-level communication between Autopsy, Flask API, and Ollama-hosted LLMs over a VPN-secured university GPU server. (Note: IP addresses shown are anonymised for privacy.)

Each message was submitted to the LLM with a structured system prompt to guide entity recognition. The schema was based on spaCy, a widely adopted open-source NLP library. To enhance forensic relevance, I appended domain-specific contextual tags (e.g., BANK, TRAVEL) under a custom field called TAGS, allowing the model to capture the broader intent of the message in addition to fine-grained entity extraction. The model’s output was returned in a strict JSON format, ensuring consistent parsing and reintegration into the forensic pipeline.

While early experiments relied on intuitive groupings such as asset, identity, and location, this approach lacked linguistic granularity. I transitioned to a formally defined categorisation schema grounded in spaCy’s entity taxonomy to improve extraction accuracy. The final schema comprised 18 categories: PERSON, NORP, FAC, ORG, GPE, LOC, PRODUCT, EVENT, WORK_OF_ART, LAW, LANGUAGE, DATE, TIME, PERCENT, MONEY, QUANTITY, ORDINAL, and CARDINAL.

This structured classification allowed the model to identify forensic signals embedded in everyday SMS content, from names, places, and transactions to temporal and legal references. The complete taxonomy with category definitions and usage examples is provided in Appendix C.

Stage IV – Output Integration

After the LLM completes entity extraction, the structured JSON response is transmitted back to the Autopsy plugin through the embedded Java HTTP server. The plugin parses each response and maps the extracted entities to custom blackboard artefacts within Autopsy’s forensic GUI.

Each artefact includes the original message, the full set of extracted NER fields, and contextual information. These artefacts are stored within Autopsy’s internal case structure and made available for filtering, searching, and visual review. This integration significantly enhances the investigator’s ability to identify relevant patterns in the data quickly.

For example, consider an investigator trying to determine how many different currencies were involved in a suspect’s SMS records. In the default Autopsy interface, this would require entering one currency keyword at a time (e.g., “USD”, “INR”, “YEN”, “GBP”) and repeating the search for each possible currency, of which there are over 150 globally. This becomes a tedious and time-consuming task and relies heavily on the investigator’s prior knowledge or assumptions about the dataset.

By contrast, the AI-assisted interface introduced through the plugin displays a dedicated CAT-CURRENCY column that isolates all extracted currency values across messages. This enables investigators to view, at a glance, the full range of currencies mentioned in the SMS corpus without needing to guess or input each currency keyword manually. Additionally, traditional keyword search is still supported, offering a hybrid interface that combines precision and usability.

To illustrate this transformation, Figure 3.3 presents a generalised before-and-after interface comparison, showing the shift from traditional keyword-based filtering to AI-assisted semantic categorisation. The detailed UI layout and screenshots are provided in Appendix E.

Figure 3.3: Representative Illustration of default keyword-based SMS filtering (left) with the enhanced plugin interface (right). The developed plugin enables semantic categorisation using NER-based columns (e.g., ORG, CURRENCY, AMOUNT), improving usability and forensic insight.

Keyword Search (eg. "USD")

Data Artifact	Artifact Source	SMS Text
(Android-1)	mmssms.db	SMS1
	mmssms.db	SMS2
	mmssms.db	SMS3
(Android-1)	mmssms.db	SMS1
	mmssms.db	SMS2
	mmssms.db	SMS3

Figure 3.3a: Autopsy UI Illustration

+ Keyword Search

			AI Assisted Categorisation (Total 18 Columns)		
Data Artifact	Artifact Source	SMS Text	CAT-ORG	CAT-CURRENCY	CAT-AMOUNT
(Android-1)	mmssms.db	SMS1	WALLMART	USD	110.0
	mmssms.db	SMS2			
	mmssms.db	SMS3	IKEA	GBP	34.56
(Android-1)	mmssms.db	SMS1			
	mmssms.db	SMS2			
	mmssms.db	SMS3	SUSHI	YEN	1000.0

Figure 3.3b: My Plugin UI Illustration

Stage V – Performance Evaluation

I employed a hybrid-layered evaluation strategy combining statistical analysis and automated model-based scoring to assess the accuracy and reliability of the LLM's categorisation capabilities. First, I manually annotated a representative ground truth dataset of 100 SMS messages. Each message was examined and labelled across entity categories, enabling precise measurement of the model's classification performance.

The evaluation used established statistical metrics, including Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Accuracy, Specificity, and MCC. These metrics provided a strong quantitative assessment of the model's ability to identify relevant entities without overclassification or omission.

I integrated a custom-built G-Eval framework to scale the evaluation beyond the manually reviewed subset. This model-driven evaluator applied prompt-based scoring to assess factual consistency, contextual alignment, and relevance of LLM outputs across a broader dataset of up to 1,000 messages. The G-Eval results mirrored the manual benchmark scores, validating its use as an efficient and reliable alternative for large-scale forensic evaluation.

Stage VI – Model Refinement & Optimisation

Model refinement in Component A was guided by aggregate evaluation metrics such as Accuracy, F1 Score, and MCC. If performance indicators revealed poor entity recognition or excessive false positives, I applied targeted adjustments to either the prompt structure or the underlying language model.

Refinement was approached through two primary strategies:

- **Prompt Optimisation:** I revised the structure, ordering, and clarity of entity definitions within the prompt to minimise ambiguity and reduce hallucinated outputs.
- **Model Selection:** In cases where prompt tuning proved insufficient, I transitioned to a more capable LLM (e.g., from Gemma2 2B to 9B or Llama 8B to GPT-4o) to improve contextual understanding and categorisation fidelity.

This iterative refinement ensured that the final configuration aligned with the performance expectations required for practical forensic use.

3.3.3 Prompt Design

I configured the LLM using a domain-adapted prompt grounded in NER principles to enable structured entity extraction from SMS messages. The goal was to extract relevant forensic entities in a consistent, verifiable JSON format suitable for downstream integration into Autopsy’s artefact system.

The final prompt defined 18 entity types, based on spaCy’s NER schema (refer to section 3.3.2-stage III), along with a custom TAGS field to capture the overall semantic context of the message. The prompt enforced a rigid JSON schema to ensure output integrity, requiring each entity field to be populated, using a dash (“-”) when no relevant content was detected.

This strict formatting was maintained by embedding the following constraints directly within the prompt:

- Explicit definitions for each category label.
- Mandatory population of all fields (no omissions or skipped entries).
- JSON-only response enforcement with structural validation.
- Rejection of free-text replies or loosely formatted outputs.
- During prompt experimentation, three structures were tested:

Short prompts (entity names only) produced insufficient context and low accuracy. Extensive prompts (with definitions and multiple examples) introduced hallucinations, particularly in low-information SMS messages. Medium-length prompts, which included concise definitions without overloading the model context window, achieved the best balance between recall and precision. The finalised prompt was applied uniformly throughout Component A evaluations and is included in Appendix C for reproducibility.

3.4 COMPONENT-B: DATA SUMMARISATION

3.4.1 Architecture and Integration Design

Component B addresses the challenge of summarising unstructured chat data, which typically spans multiple platforms and lacks the structured schema required for traditional forensic triage. Given the limitations of the Autopsy plugin environment, particularly its restricted support for Python libraries and modern frontend technologies, I implemented a standalone architecture based on modular, interoperable components.

Chat messages were extracted from Android device images using ALEAPP (Alexis B., 2020), a forensic artefact parser capable of processing app-based communication logs. The parsed data was exported in CSV format and transmitted to a Flask-based server for further processing. This server was a bridge between the forensic data layer and a local instance of Ollama, which hosted the summarisation models. Models such as Gemma2 9B were deployed locally on a GPU server.

To visualise the results, I built a responsive web interface that allowed forensic analysts to interact with summarised chat sessions. The frontend was designed using HTML, JavaScript, and Tailwind CSS, and was rendered dynamically through Flask routes. Investigators could browse summaries chronologically, expand them to see the original messages, and apply filters based on time windows or chat platforms.

This decoupled design ensured maximum flexibility: forensic data never left the analyst’s environment, model inference remained local, and the UI could be updated or extended independently of the backend. It also allowed for modular evaluation workflows, including iterative feedback loops and visualisation enhancements. The next subsection provides a high-level flowchart of this architecture.

3.4.2 Implementation Workflow

This subsection outlines the end-to-end implementation process for Component B: Data Summarisation via a Standalone Interface. The workflow spans six core stages, from data extraction to summarisation evaluation, each designed to preserve forensic integrity while enabling scalable AI-driven interpretation. A high-level flowchart summarising the architecture and data flow is presented below.

Figure 3.4: End-to-End Workflow for Component B – Chats & SMS Summarisation

Stage I – Dataset Collection

To simulate realistic forensic conditions, I sourced mobile chat data from Android forensic images using ALEAPP, an open-source tool widely used for extracting mobile artefacts. The datasets were obtained from public repositories such as Digital Corpora and with lab-generated logs to ensure diversity across platforms like SMS, WhatsApp, and Facebook Messenger.

ALEAPP extracted structured records containing metadata such as timestamps, sender-recipient pairs, and message bodies, which were exported in CSV format. This structured yet unlabelled dataset provided a suitable foundation for testing LLM-driven summarisation under forensic conditions, while minimising the need for extensive manual annotation.

Stage II – Data Ingestion

I first grouped individual messages into coherent conversations to prepare the data for LLM-based summarisation. This was achieved by applying a 10-minute time-gap threshold between messages from

the same platform. If the interval between two messages exceeded the threshold, or if the message originated from a different platform, the system considered it the start of a new conversation. This approach simulates natural breaks in communication and allows forensic analysts to focus on temporally coherent threads.

In implementation, I sorted all messages by platform (e.g., SMS, WhatsApp) and timestamp. A Python script then calculated time differences between consecutive entries and dynamically assigned Conversation IDs whenever the threshold was exceeded. I also normalised timestamp formats and resolved timezone inconsistencies to maintain temporal integrity.

The resulting structured data, segmented by conversation, was stored in a unified CSV file, which served as the direct input for LLM-driven summarisation in the next stage. Figure 3.4.2 visually represents the ingestion and preprocessing workflow, illustrating the transition from raw chat logs to structured conversational blocks suitable for LLM processing.

Figure 3.5: Chat Data Preprocessing Pipeline for Summarisation.

Raw chat messages are exported in CSV format, normalised for timestamp inconsistencies, and grouped into conversations based on time-gap thresholds before being submitted to the LLM for summarisation.

Stage III – LLM Communication & Data Summarisation

To ensure contextual integrity, I submitted each grouped conversation block, rather than isolated messages, to the LLM. This allowed the model to access full dialogue flow, resulting in more accurate and coherent forensic summaries. The summarisation process was executed using a locally hosted LLM (Gemma2 9B) via the Ollama API, accessed through a Flask server.

For each conversation, I constructed a structured prompt containing the complete sequence of messages and submitted it to the LLM for summarisation. The summary was then evaluated using the G-Eval framework. Summaries scoring below the 90% quality threshold triggered a refinement loop: I appended G-Eval’s feedback to the prompt and resubmitted the conversation for regeneration. This iterative process continued until the generated summary satisfied the defined quality criteria. The validated outputs were stored alongside their evaluation scores for visualisation and final review.

Figure 3.8 presents a visual overview of this summarisation-feedback loop, outlines how the LLM collaborates with G-Eval scoring to ensure consistently high forensic quality standards.

Stage IV – Output Integration

I exported all finalised summaries into structured CSV files before visualisation to facilitate efficient review and interaction. This pre-processing approach decoupled summary generation from frontend rendering, ensuring a faster and more responsive user interface. The same Flask server used for LLM inference was extended to serve a lightweight web interface for displaying conversation summaries.

In View 1, I designed a timeline-based interface using the vis-timeline JavaScript library. The Flask server delivered a JSON file containing all conversation summaries, which the frontend displayed

chronologically. Users could interact with each node on the timeline to expand and view the corresponding messages from that conversation block.

In View 2, I adopted a more flexible template-driven approach using Flask and Jinja2. This view supported two ways of interacting with the summarised data. The first was a timeline grouper, where users could define custom time intervals, such as five minutes or one day, to organise messages into logical conversation segments. Each group included a summary and an expandable section that displayed the original messages. The second interaction mode allowed users to filter summaries by messaging platform, such as WhatsApp or Telegram, presenting grouped summaries with timestamps and message tables tailored to each platform.

Both interfaces rendered pre-processed summaries stored in CSV format and did not depend on real-time model inference. This architecture ensured scalability, fast loading, and seamless user experience during forensic review.

Figures 3.6 and 3.7 illustrate this transformation by visually comparing Autopsy’s original message pane and the developed AI-assisted summarisation interface. An actual snapshot of the UI is attached in Appendix E.

Figure 3.6: A representative illustration of the traditional Autopsy interface, showing how raw chat records appear in list format. Messages are displayed sequentially with basic metadata but without summarisation or conversational grouping. This general view highlights the limitations investigators may face when interpreting unstructured message logs.

Timestamp	Description
Date/Time	Source : Direction : UUID/GUID : Actual Message
12/04/2025 18:39	WhatsApp Message: Incoming from b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676 → Hi John, how are you?
13/04/2025 10:15	WhatsApp Message: Outgoing to 9c54d0a2-f6e1-4dbe-a2a7-23b5bdb3e3c1 → Doing well! The project is coming along. You?
14/04/2025 9:42	WhatsApp Message: Incoming from b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676 → Mostly fine, but running into a few issues.
15/04/2025 16:27	WhatsApp Message: Outgoing to b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676 → Let's catch up and go over them.
16/04/2025 13:05	WhatsApp Message: Incoming from b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676 → Sure. Starbucks at 3 PM works? It's on Main Street.
16/04/2025 13:08	WhatsApp Message: Outgoing to b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676 → Perfect. See you there.

Figure 3.7: A conceptual representation of the custom-built summarisation interface developed in Component B. The UI allows investigators to view AI-generated summaries grouped by conversation ID and message type. Users can inspect the underlying message blocks by selecting a conversation to validate forensic accuracy. This structured and time-filtered view enhances readability and evidential review

User defined Time GAP decide how many Conversation ID appears in the search (e.g. 30 min)

Conversation ID	Duration (Sec)	Message Type	Message Summary
1	141:00:00	Whatsapp Message	John was contacted via WhatsApp by another individual to check in and discuss the progress of a project. John responded that the project was mostly fine but had some issues. The two agreed to meet in person to discuss the problems further. A specific plan was made to meet at Starbucks at 3 PM on Main Street.
2	30:00:00	Viber	The user informed a third party via Viber that John would be meeting them at Starbucks at 3 PM. The message advised the third person to arrive at the same location to intercept or catch up with John. This implies some level of coordination or intent to confront or observe John's meeting at the designated place and time

→ Categorized Conversation ID: 1 (User click any Conversation ID row to get details of chat to reconfirm the summary correctness)

Timestamp	From	To	Message
16/04/2025 14:51	b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676	a4e7d103-9f2e-44cc-b23d-0a9382c1db55	Hi John, how are you?
16/04/2025 14:52	a4e7d103-9f2e-44cc-b23d-0a9382c1db55	b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676	Doing well! The project is coming along. You?
16/04/2025 14:54	b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676	a4e7d103-9f2e-44cc-b23d-0a9382c1db55	Mostly fine, but running into a few issues.
16/04/2025 14:56	a4e7d103-9f2e-44cc-b23d-0a9382c1db55	b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676	Let's catch up and go over them.
16/04/2025 14:58	b2989af7-e4dc-4821-bf48-3468c82f6676	a4e7d103-9f2e-44cc-b23d-0a9382c1db55	Sure. Starbucks at 3 PM works? It's on Main Street.

Stage V – Performance Evaluation

To assess the accuracy and reliability of LLM-generated summaries, I established a human-annotated ground truth by manually writing summaries for each conversation in the dataset. These human-written references served as the benchmark against which model-generated outputs were evaluated.

Initially, I tested traditional word-overlap metrics such as BLEU and ROUGE. However, these methods were ultimately discarded, as they failed to account for semantic equivalence and could not detect hallucinated content, a critical shortcoming in forensic contexts where factual consistency is essential.

To address these limitations, I adopted a model-based evaluation approach. I used BERTScore to measure the semantic similarity between the AI-generated summaries and the human-written ground truth. Additionally, I implemented G-Eval, a custom prompt-based evaluation framework that uses LLMs to assess coherence, factual accuracy, and linguistic fluency. G-Eval aligned closely with BERTScore results and provided more detailed qualitative feedback on summary quality.

I also performed manual spot checks on 5–10% of the summaries to ensure forensic integrity. These reviews validated that the generated outputs conformed to the intended summary objectives and met domain-specific forensic accuracy and interpretability standards.

Stage VI – Model Refinement & Optimisation

Component B's model refinement process was guided by Component A's findings, where different LLMs were benchmarked for categorisation accuracy and forensic robustness. Gemma2 9B was selected for summarisation based on those results due to its balance between contextual reasoning capability and on-device privacy.

To improve output quality further, I employed an iterative summarisation loop driven by G-Eval scores. If a summary's score dropped below 90%, the system dynamically appended the LLM's errors, identified through G-Eval feedback, back into the prompt as correction cues. The revised prompt was then resubmitted to the LLM for a second attempt. The (Madaan et al., 2023) paper supports iterative refinement to improve LLM's initial outputs.

Figure 3.8: Iterative LLM Summarisation and G-Eval Refinement Loop.

The LLM summarises each conversation and evaluates it using G-Eval. If the quality score falls below the defined threshold, the summary is revised based on G-Eval feedback and resubmitted until it meets forensic quality standards.

This refinement cycle continued until the summary met the required accuracy threshold. The iterative loop can be expressed as:

$S_i = f(P_i)$, where $P_{i+1} = P_i + G\text{-Eval Feedback}$ until $G(S_i) \geq \tau$

Where:

- S_i is the summary at iteration i
- P_i is the prompt at iteration i
- $G(S_i)$ is the G-Eval score for S_i
- $\tau = 0.90$ is the minimum acceptable score threshold
- f is the LLM summarisation function

This loop ensured hallucinations were minimised, factual accuracy was reinforced, and summaries aligned more closely with forensic objectives. In addition, user-based spot-checking during evaluation helped detect nuanced issues like contextual bias or critical omission, further informing prompt adjustments. Combining model selection with feedback-driven refinement, this hybrid strategy enabled Component B to achieve performance and trustworthiness in summarisation tasks.

3.4.3 Prompt Design

I developed a structured and dynamic prompt template tailored specifically for forensic conversations to generate semantically accurate and context-aware summaries. Each prompt consisted of three main components: (i) a task-specific instruction, (ii) a unique conversation identifier, and (iii) a sequential list of timestamped messages that retained platform and temporal context.

An example prompt used during local inference via Ollama is shown below:

Generate a concise summary of the conversation below.

Conversation ID: 213

Messages:

2024-04-01 10:45:00 - (WhatsApp): Hey, did you receive the invoice?

2024-04-01 10:46:10 - (WhatsApp): Yes, I got it this morning.

2024-04-01 10:47:23 - (WhatsApp): I'll forward it to finance now.

This design provided sufficient contextual cues, such as chronology and platform, without overloading the LLM's input window. To avoid distracting the model from the core conversational content, sender IDs and other inline metadata were deliberately excluded. The goal was to keep the prompt clean and readable while retaining enough information for temporal and contextual inference.

To assess the accuracy of generated summaries, I adopted G-Eval, a model-based evaluation framework built on DeepEval's Correctness metric and executed via the OpenAI API. G-Eval prompts a second LLM to assess the quality of the summary by comparing it with the original conversation using structured reasoning steps:

```

GEval(
  name="Correctness",
  criteria="Determine whether the summary accurately reflects the conversation messages.",
  evaluation_steps=[
    "Check if the summary captures the key points of the conversation.",
    "Ensure no important details are omitted from the summary.",
    "Verify that the summary does not introduce any incorrect information."
  ],
  evaluation_params=[
    LLMTestCaseParams.INPUT,
    LLMTestCaseParams.ACTUAL_OUTPUT
  ],
  verbose_mode=True
)

```

A minimum G-Eval threshold of 90% was enforced. Summaries falling below this score were automatically rejected and reprocessed in a new iteration. In such cases, G-Eval's feedback was appended to the prompt to guide the LLM's following response. For instance, the revised prompt would include:

```
"The previous summary was evaluated and scored below 90%. Refine the summary to capture the key points of the conversation better. Additional Feedback: <G-Eval feedback inserted here>."
```

This feedback-driven refinement loop allowed the model to self-correct based on its previous outputs, improving factual alignment, coherence, and narrative quality.

4 RESULTS AND EVALUATION

4.1 OVERVIEW OF EVALUATION STRATEGY

This section presents the evaluation strategy designed to measure the effectiveness, reliability, and applicability of LLMs in digital forensic workflows. The evaluation is structured around five research objectives and divided into two experimental components: Component A (Data Categorisation) and Component B (Data Summarisation).

As briefly outlined in Section 3, the methodology combines quantitative and qualitative assessment techniques. For quantitative analysis, I used statistical classification metrics such as Precision, Recall, F1-score, Specificity, Accuracy, and MCC. I employed BERTScore and a custom-developed evaluation model named G-Eval to assess semantic fidelity and contextual correctness. The latter provides a model-driven assessment of the coherence, factual accuracy, and relevance of LLM-generated outputs.

In Component A, I evaluated the accuracy of SMS message categorisation using a manually labelled ground truth dataset. The evaluation relied primarily on statistical metrics, and for scalability, I used G-Eval to semi-automate the process for larger datasets.

In Component B, which involved summarising chat conversations, I found traditional word-overlap metrics like BLEU and ROUGE inadequate for assessing forensic accuracy. Instead, I relied on BERTScore and G-Eval to evaluate semantic alignment and contextual integrity. Additionally, I performed manual spot checks on 5–10% of the summaries to identify hallucinations, factual omissions, or any signs of bias in the generated content.

This evaluation also explores the comparative benefits of manual versus AI-assisted workflows regarding time savings and investigative efficiency. Throughout both components, I assessed multiple LLMs, including lightweight models like Gemma2 2B, mid-sized open models like Llama 8B and Gemma2 9B, and a high-parameter proprietary model, GPT-4o (with over 175B parameters). These comparisons helped analyse how model size, architecture, and deployment method influence the trade-offs between performance, resource demands, and forensic applicability.

4.2 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 1 – TIME EFFICIENCY

This section addresses Objective 1 of the study: “Assess time savings in digital forensic investigations using LLMs.” The goal was to evaluate whether integrating LLMs into forensic workflows could significantly reduce the time required for investigative tasks.

To measure time efficiency, I conducted a user study involving six participants. Each participant completed two task scenarios, one for each project component, under manual and LLM-assisted conditions. I recorded the time taken in each scenario and calculated percentage improvements.

The study setup simulated real-world forensic tasks:

- For **Component A (SMS Categorisation)**, users were asked to identify all currency-related transactions from a dataset of 100 SMS records.
- For **Component B (Chat Summarisation)**, users were tasked with summarising one hour’s worth of conversation logs collected from messaging platforms like WhatsApp, IMO, and Facebook.

Table 4.1: Comparison of Manual vs LLM-Assisted Task Completion Time

This table compares the time required to complete two digital forensics-related tasks using manual methods versus assistance with LLM. The tasks include identifying currency mentions in SMS data and generating a cross-platform chat summary. Percentage time savings are also shown, highlighting the efficiency gains enabled by LLM integration. Full experimental setup and logs are available in Appendix F

TASK	COMPONENT	TIME (MANUAL)	TIME (LLM-ASSISTED)	TIME SAVED (%)
Identify all currency mentions in 100 SMS records	Component A	~9.8 mins	~2.1 mins	~78.3%
Generate a 1-hour chat summary (cross-platform)	Component B	~11.2 mins	~4.7 mins	~58.0%

These results confirm a substantial reduction in the time required for key forensic tasks when using LLM-based assistance. In Component A, LLM-driven entity recognition allowed users to bypass repetitive keyword searches, replacing them with instantly filterable semantic tags. In Component B, summarisation tools accelerated chat log interpretation while maintaining clarity and relevance.

In addition to time savings, I also collected qualitative feedback from participants using a simplified stress-perception scale. Most users reported lower cognitive load, greater task confidence, and an improved overall experience when using LLM-assisted tools.

These findings validate the hypothesis that LLM integration can improve time efficiency and usability in digital forensic investigations, primarily for routine or repetitive tasks.

4.3 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 2A (DATA CATEGORISATION PERFORMANCE)

4.3.1 Goal of Evaluation

This section evaluates the performance of LLMs in automating forensic data categorisation, as implemented in Component A via the custom Autopsy plugin. The objective was to determine whether LLMs could accurately identify and classify forensic entities such as currencies, names, locations, and dates from SMS messages. These tasks traditionally require tedious manual review.

4.3.2 Dataset and Metrics

I created a labelled ground truth dataset of 100 SMS records to benchmark model performance. Each message was manually tagged as:

- **Positive** – Containing one or more extractable forensic entities (i.e., values \neq “-”)
- **Negative** – Containing no valid entities (i.e., all values = “-”)

The plugin then processed these messages using various LLMs, and the outputs were compared against the labelled truth using six forensic-relevant metrics:

Table 4.2: Key Evaluation Metrics for Forensic Categorisation Accuracy

Summary of statistical metrics used to evaluate the classification performance of LLMs in Component A, including their definitions and forensic relevance.

METRIC	WHAT IT MEASURES	WHY IT MATTERS IN FORENSICS
Precision	% of predicted entities that were correct	Reduces false alerts and improves reporting accuracy
Recall	% of actual entities that were detected	Ensures no critical evidence is overlooked
F1 Score	Harmonic mean of precision and recall	Reflects overall model balance and reliability
Accuracy	Overall correct predictions	General success indicator
Specificity	True negatives are correctly identified	Prevents irrelevant matches from cluttering the results
MCC	Balanced score for imbalanced datasets	Reliable in cases with sparse or skewed entity distributions

(See Appendix D for complete formulas and category-wise breakdown.)

4.3.3 Results Across Models

Four LLMs were evaluated: Gemma2 2B, Llama 8B, **Gemma2 9B**, and **GPT-4o**. Their comparative performance is summarised below:

Table 4.3: Comparative Performance of LLMs in SMS Entity Categorisation

Evaluation results of four different LLMs based on classification metrics and G-Eval scores, highlighting trade-offs between model size, accuracy, and deployment suitability in forensic environments.

MODEL	MCC	RECALL (TPR)	SELECTIVITY (TNR)	PRECISION	ACCURACY	F1 SCORE	G-EVAL (%)
Gemma2 2B	-0.3171	10.58	48.74	4.422	41.76	6.237	–
Llama 8B	0.25255	67.92	64.27	29.88	64.94	41.5	66.3
Gemma2 9B	0.5383	63.48	91.05	61.39	86%	64.42	89.60
GPT-4o >175B	0.7183	67.92	97.48	85.78	92.06%	75.81	91.70

- **GPT-4o** achieved the highest overall performance with >92% accuracy and an MCC of 0.71.
- **Gemma2 9B** offered a practical open-source solution, reaching 86% accuracy, a balanced F1 score, and a strong MCC of 0.5383.
- **Llama 8B** performed adequately but required more inference time.
- **Gemma2 2B** struggled significantly with <50% accuracy and a negative MCC, confirming that smaller models underperform on complex forensic data.

4.3.4 G-Eval Validation and Human Spot Checks

G-Eval was used to semantically assess the output across larger samples to complement the statistical evaluation. Its scores, focused on factual coherence and label consistency, correlated within $\pm 3\%$ of human-verified results for high-performing models. Manual spot-checks (5–10% of all records) confirmed that categorised entities were consistent with forensic expectations and contained no hallucinated values.

4.3.5 Conclusion

This evaluation confirmed that LLMs can reliably support forensic categorisation tasks when applied to structured message data. Models with parameter counts exceeding 8-9 billion (e.g., Gemma2 9B, GPT-4o) consistently demonstrated strong performance across statistical and model-based evaluation metrics. These higher-capacity models exhibited improved ability to identify nuanced forensic entities, making them well-suited for integration in investigative workflows, particularly when balanced against considerations of deployment viability, data privacy, and computational resources.

Both traditional classification metrics and semantic scoring frameworks, such as G-Eval, provided a well-rounded validation methodology, supporting LLM’s scalable and trustworthy adoption in forensic tools like Autopsy.

Figure 4.1: Accuracy and G-Eval Score Comparison for SMS Categorisation Models

Visual comparison of statistical accuracy and model-based G-Eval scores across four LLMs, illustrating the correlation between semantic evaluation and traditional performance metrics. The red dashed line indicates the 90% threshold used for summary acceptance.

4.4 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 2B (DATA SUMMARISATION QUALITY)

4.4.1 Goal of Evaluation

This section presents the results of Component B, which evaluated the effectiveness of LLMs in summarising forensic chat conversations recovered from Android mobile images. The goal was to

determine whether LLMs could generate concise, contextually accurate summaries while minimising hallucination, bias, or omission of critical forensic elements.

4.4.2 Dataset and Metric Setup

As outlined in Section 3.4, the chat data used for evaluation was extracted using ALEAPP from two Android forensic images: Android 7 (A7) and Android 12 (A12). The model selected for summarisation was **Gemma2 9B**, chosen based on its strong performance in Component A and its suitability for privacy-sensitive deployments.

To assess the quality of LLM-generated summaries, two complementary model-based metrics were employed:

- **G-Eval (%)**: A prompt-based evaluation method that scores summaries on factual coherence, fluency, and relevance, with 90% as the minimum quality threshold.
- **BERTScore (range 0–1)**: A semantic similarity metric that compares the model-generated summary with a manually written reference, capturing alignment in meaning and context.

4.4.3 Evaluation Results

Gemma2 9B demonstrated consistently strong summarisation performance across both Android datasets. As shown in **Table 4.4**, the average **G-Eval** score exceeded **90%**, confirming the factual accuracy and coherence of the AI-generated summaries. The **BERTScore** remained above **0.92** in both cases, indicating high semantic similarity with the human-authored reference summaries.

Table 4.4: G-Eval and BERTScore performance across Android 7 and Android 12 datasets for summarisation quality evaluation using Gemma2 9B.

DATASET ID	GEVAL (%)	BERT SCORE
A7	96.2	0.9319
A12	93.3	0.9288

4.4.4 Semantic Validation and Spot Checks

Approximately 5–10% of the summaries were manually spot-checked to further validate the outputs. These checks confirmed that no significant hallucinations or misrepresentations occurred. A few instances contained overly broad phrasing or missed minor nuances, which were corrected by refining the summarisation prompt.

The summarisation process entered a refinement loop in cases where G-Eval scores fell below the 90% threshold. This loop automatically appended G-Eval feedback to the prompt and resubmitted the conversation to the LLM until the output satisfied quality criteria.

Figure 4.2 illustrates further comparison by visualising the relative performance across both datasets. While Android 7 yielded slightly higher scores, the margin of difference was minimal. These results suggest that the summarisation model generalises well across Android versions and message types, maintaining forensic reliability.

Figure 4.2: Visual comparison of summarisation quality using G-Eval (%) and BERTScore (0–1) across Android 7 and Android 12 forensic datasets.

4.4.5 Conclusion

Component B confirms that LLMs, particularly mid-to-large-scale models such as Gemma2 9B, can reliably produce high-quality, semantically accurate summaries for forensic chat data. While the summarisation pipeline supports substantial automation, manual review remains essential for high-stakes use cases to mitigate the risk of subtle omissions or misinterpretations. The consistent success of both evaluation metrics reinforces the potential of LLMs as valuable assistive agents in forensic reporting and triage.

4.5 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 3 (PERFORMANCE THRESHOLDS FOR LLMs IN DIGITAL FORENSICS)

This section evaluates the performance impact of model scale and licensing type (open-source vs. closed-source) on the forensic applicability of LLMs. The objective was to determine the minimum viable model size and assess whether open-source models could provide sufficient accuracy for digital forensic tasks compared to proprietary alternatives.

4.5.1 Objective and Context

In forensic investigations, the choice of LLM is influenced by performance and operational and legal constraints such as cost, data privacy, explainability, and offline accessibility. Closed-source models like GPT-4o provide high accuracy but may pose limitations in forensic environments due to their proprietary nature and API dependency. This evaluation aims to identify which model configurations (size and source) offer the best trade-off between forensic reliability and practical deployment.

The focus is assessing whether smaller or open-source LLMs can meet forensic standards or whether large-scale proprietary models are indispensable for reliable categorisation and interpretation.

4.5.2 Evaluation Criteria

All models were tested in parallel using the standardised prompts and task configurations described earlier in Sections 3.3 (Categorisation) and 3.4 (Summarisation). Forensic categorisation was treated as a multi-label classification task, where each message was independently evaluated for the presence or absence of specific entities such as DATE, MONEY, and LOCATION. Each of these entity-level evaluations aligned with a binary classification logic.

The MCC was selected as the primary evaluation metric due to its robustness in handling imbalanced binary classification problems, a common occurrence in digital forensics where certain entities appear far less frequently than others. Unlike accuracy or F1 score, which may be biased by class distribution, MCC considers all four elements of the confusion matrix (true positives, true negatives, false positives, false negatives) to produce a more balanced and reliable score. This metric has been recommended for similar classification tasks in prior studies, including (Chicco and Jurman, 2020), who demonstrated its advantages over traditional metrics in evaluating binary outcomes.

In addition to MCC, supplementary metrics such as Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Accuracy, and G-Eval were used to provide a holistic understanding of model performance. While MCC remained the benchmark for determining the minimum viable model scale, these additional metrics helped assess practical deployment readiness.

As listed in **Table 4.5**, four models were compared:

Table 4.5: List of models compared

MODEL	TYPE	PARAMETERS
Gemma2 2B	Open-source	~2 billion
Llama 8B	Open-source	~8 billion
Gemma2 9B	Open-source	~9 billion
GPT-4o	Closed-source	>175 billion

4.5.3 Results and Visual Comparison

The evaluation revealed a strong correlation between model performance, parameter scale, and licensing type (open vs. closed source). As summarised in Table 4.6, four models were tested for forensic categorisation using standard classification prompts. Each model's output was evaluated using key statistical and model-based metrics

Figure 4.3 presents the MCC scores for each model to enhance interpretability. MCC was selected as the primary comparative metric due to its balanced handling of both positive and negative classifications, as discussed in Section 4.5.2.

Table 4.6: Comparative performance of four LLMs (Gemma2 2B, Llama 8B, Gemma2 9B, GPT-4o) across statistical and model-based metrics for forensic categorisation, including MCC, Precision, Accuracy, and G-Eval score.

MODEL	MCC	RECALL (TPR)	SELECTIVITY (TNR)	PRECISION	ACCURACY	F1 SCORE	G-EVAL (%)
Gemma2 2B	-0.3171	10.58	48.74	4.422	41.76	6.24	N/A
Llama 8B	0.2525	67.92	64.27	29.88	64.94	41.50	66.3
Gemma2 9B	0.5383	63.48	91.05	61.39	86.00	64.42	89.60
GPT-4o	0.7183	67.92	97.48	85.78	92.06	75.81	91.70

Figure 4.3: MCC score comparison across models, illustrating the effect of model scale and type (open vs. closed source) on forensic categorisation reliability.

The results indicate that:

- **Gemma2 2B** performed poorly across all metrics, with a negative MCC score indicating severe inconsistency in classification.
- **Llama 8B** offered moderate improvements, but its relatively low precision and G-Eval score limited its forensic suitability.
- **Gemma2 9B** achieved high performance, surpassing 85% accuracy in Component A and 91% overall in the study. This nearly matches GPT-4o in G-Eval score, making it the most practical open-source candidate.
- **GPT-4o**, as expected, outperformed all models in statistical and semantic metrics but comes with deployment trade-offs due to its proprietary nature and external API requirements.

These comparative results reinforce the influence of model size and architecture on forensic applicability, particularly in classification tasks involving nuanced semantic extraction.

4.5.4 Conclusion

This evaluation confirms that while large-scale proprietary models like GPT-4o offer the highest performance, well-optimised open-source alternatives such as Gemma2 9B can deliver comparably reliable results in forensic NLP tasks. Gemma2 9B consistently exceeded 85% in statistical metrics and achieved over 90% in model-based evaluations such as G-Eval, demonstrating its effectiveness for both categorisation and summarisation tasks.

In contrast, smaller models, those below 8B parameters, showed insufficient accuracy and stability for forensic use, as reflected by negative or low MCC scores. These findings suggest that a minimum scale of approximately 8B parameters is necessary for dependable forensic performance when using LLMs, particularly in fine-grained semantic classification tasks.

With selective human oversight, LLMs at this threshold can be safely deployed in privacy-sensitive environments, offering a viable balance between accuracy, operational flexibility, and forensic integrity.

4.6 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 4 (COMPARATIVE METRIC ANALYSIS)

This section analyses and compares the evaluation metrics used to assess the performance of LLMs across both components, categorisation (Component A) and summarisation (Component B). The goal was to determine which metrics were most appropriate for forensic applications, particularly regarding interpretability, domain relevance, and their ability to detect hallucinations or factual inconsistencies.

4.6.1 Metrics Applied to Component A – Forensic Categorisation

Component A focused on structured forensic data (SMS), where the primary task involved categorising messages based on named entities and forensic labels. Since this task required classification in the presence of imbalanced class distributions, the evaluation emphasised statistical robustness, interpretability, and domain alignment.

As summarised in **Table 4.7**, six statistical metrics were selected to evaluate LLM performance: Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Specificity, Accuracy, and MCC. These metrics were chosen for their relevance to forensic use cases, particularly where false positives and negatives must be balanced carefully. MCC was selected based on its proven reliability in imbalanced datasets and its ability to account for all four elements of the confusion matrix.

Other metrics, such as AUROC, Cohen’s Kappa, and Log Loss, were considered but excluded due to overlapping functionality with the chosen metrics or limited practical interpretability for multi-entity text classification. Appendix A provides a full list of the reviewed metrics and their rationale for inclusion or exclusion.

Table 4.7: Metrics considered for Component A

METRIC	FINAL DECISION	STUDY FINDINGS
Precision	Selected	Reduced false positives by isolating only relevant forensic entities.
Recall	Selected	Ensured critical forensic data (e.g., transactions) was not overlooked.
F1 Score	Selected	A balanced performance metric is ideal for evidence triage accuracy.
Specificity	Selected	Minimised misclassification of non-forensic content.
MCC (Matthews Corr. Coeff.)	Selected	Most reliable in imbalanced class settings, offering balanced evaluation.
ROUGE / BLEU / BERTScore	Rejected	These metrics focus on text similarity, which did not align with the needs of classification-based entity extraction.

4.6.2 Metrics Applied to Component B – Forensic Summarisation

Component B involved summarisation of unstructured chat data, where coherence, factual accuracy, and semantic fidelity were more critical than surface-level keyword matching. The evaluation, therefore, required metrics capable of assessing linguistic similarity, contextual correctness, and narrative consistency. As summarised in **Table 4.8**, three key metrics were selected:

Table 4.8: Metrics considered for Component B

METRIC	FINAL DECISION	STUDY FINDINGS
BERTScore	Selected	Captured semantic alignment between AI-generated and human summaries.
G-Eval	Selected	Evaluated coherence, factuality, and hallucination risk in forensic summaries.
ROUGE	Rejected	Focused on surface overlap, unable to assess factual accuracy or paraphrasing.
BLEU	Rejected	Too rigid for forensic summaries; penalised, rephrased, yet contextually correct to
Manual Spot-Check (5–10%)	Selected	Required to validate critical legal detail preservation and detect edge-case errors.

- **BERTScore**, based on contextual embeddings from BERT (Devlin et al., 2019), measures semantic similarity between the generated and reference summaries. Its alignment with meaning rather than surface form made it well-suited for evaluating forensic summarisation.
- **G-Eval**, an LLM-based evaluation framework (Zhou et al., 2023), assessed summary coherence, factual grounding, and hallucination risk. This model-based evaluator aligned closely with forensic expectations by flagging omissions and misleading inclusions.
- **Manual Spot-Check (5–10%)** was included as a final layer to validate critical forensic details, especially in high-risk edge cases where AI outputs could misinterpret intent or timeline.

Metrics like ROUGE and BLEU, traditionally used for machine translation and summarisation, were rejected. They focus on surface-level n-gram overlap and penalise legitimate paraphrasing, a significant drawback in forensic settings where exact wording may differ but meaning must remain intact (Fabbri et al., 2021).

4.6.3 Conclusion

While Component A benefited from classical statistical metrics (e.g., Precision, Recall, MCC), these were inadequate for assessing unstructured outputs in Component B. Metrics such as BERTScore and G-Eval offered more profound insight into semantic alignment and factual consistency, which are vital in forensic reporting. This finding aligns with recent studies highlighting the limitations of ROUGE and BLEU for factual and context-aware summarisation (Zhou et al., 2023; Fabbri et al., 2021).

A hybrid evaluation strategy, combining statistical, semantic, and manual methods, emerged as the most reliable approach to validating LLM outputs in digital forensic workflows.

4.7 EVALUATION OF OBJECTIVE 5 (RISK MITIGATION AND FUTURE WORKS)

This section assesses the primary risks of integrating LLMs into forensic workflows, detailing mitigation strategies and suggested enhancements. The objective is to guarantee that AI-enhanced digital forensics stays reliable, contextually precise, legally sound, and defensible. Risks such as hallucinated content, misclassification, context loss, and interpretational bias were observed across Component A (Categorisation) and Component B (Summarisation).

Table 4.9 summarises the core risk areas, real observations from this study, the strategies currently applied to mitigate them, and future enhancements that could improve forensic reliability.

Table 4.9: Risk Identification, Observation, Mitigation, and Future Enhancements

HALLUCINATION RISK	OBSERVATION IN STUDY	CURRENT MITIGATION STRATEGY	FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS
Incorrect Entity Detection	Misclassification of names or currency in ambiguous contexts (Component A)	Cross-check with structured forensic databases and human spot checks	RAG-based AI to retrieve case-relevant contextual data
Hallucinated Content	In Component B, a few summaries initially included inferred but non-existent events	G-Eval scoring and iterative prompt refinement	Advanced LLMs (e.g., GPT-5, multimodal AI) for better contextual alignment
Context Loss in Summaries	Some early summaries lost key conversational nuance	Prompt tuning and refinement loop until $\geq 90\%$ G-Eval, plus 5–10% human review	Context-aware models trained on legal/forensic dialogues
Bias in Interpretation	Region-specific slang is misunderstood or generalised	Inclusion of diverse datasets and forensic-specific tuning	Bias detection AI to flag culturally skewed or biased interpretations
Over-reliance on AI Outputs	Investigator's risk of accepting AI output at face value	Human-in-the-loop validation and interface for raw message access	Explainable AI (XAI) tools for transparent decision making

4.7.1 Conclusion

This objective highlights that current AI-driven forensic tools can provide significant value but are not without risks. The most reliable strategy involves layered mitigation: prompt refinement, hybrid human-AI evaluation, and proactive error detection. Moving forward, incorporating RAG, context-tuned LLMs, and explainable AI frameworks will be critical to ensuring forensic AI systems are trustworthy, unbiased, and legally admissible.

5 CONCLUSIONS

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This research investigated the integration of LLMs into digital forensic workflows, with two key objectives: (1) enabling forensic Categorisation of structured SMS data via an Autopsy plugin (Component A), and (2) generating context-aware summaries of unstructured chat conversations through a standalone interface (Component B).

Component A demonstrated that LLMs, particularly models with ≥ 8 billion parameters, are highly effective for entity-level classification tasks. Statistical metrics such as Precision, Recall, F1 Score, and MCC consistently reflected performance levels above 85%, with open-source models like Gemma2 9B closely matching proprietary alternatives. This confirms the viability of LLMs for structured evidence triage within open-source forensic platforms like Autopsy.

Component B, focused on interpretive summarisation, yielded promising but more variable results. Using semantic evaluation tools like BERTScore and G-Eval, summaries aligned highly with human-written references, typically scoring above 90%. However, issues like hallucination, missing contextual detail, or overgeneralization persisted in some cases. Iterative refinement loops, driven by model feedback from G-Eval, were essential for improving output quality. These findings reaffirm the necessity of human oversight in forensic interpretation tasks.

Across both components, the evaluation established that smaller LLMs (e.g., Gemma2 2B) could not deliver forensic-grade reliability. However, 9B parameter range models offered an optimal balance between deployment feasibility and analytical precision. Open-source models running locally allowed forensic analysis to be conducted securely, without incurring privacy, cost, or dependency risks associated with cloud-based APIs.

5.2 CONTRIBUTIONS AND NOVELTY

This study contributes to forensic computing literature in several key areas:

- **Operational integration:** Unlike prior research that relies on conceptual demonstrations, this work implemented real-world integration into Autopsy and a browser-based UI, expanding forensic utility through practical tools.
- **Hybrid evaluation framework:** A novel scoring pipeline was applied, combining statistical classification metrics with semantic and model-based evaluators (e.g., G-Eval), offering more profound insights into LLM reliability.
- **Open-source model deployment:** The project addressed the underexplored challenge of running LLMs locally in air-gapped environments, enabling privacy-preserving forensic analysis without external dependencies.
- **Model benchmarking:** The research compared models by size and type, helping define the minimum viable scale for classification and summarisation tasks.

5.3 LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Despite promising results, limitations remain. Summarisation tasks in Component B revealed persistent challenges such as hallucination and semantic drift. LLMs sometimes failed to capture nuanced

conversation intent or omitted critical details, especially in messages with sarcasm, code-switching, or informal phrasing. Similarly, Component A was occasionally affected by region-specific terms or unstructured message formats.

To address these issues, future work should explore:

Fine-Tuning Locally Hosted Models with Domain-Specific Forensic Datasets

Future work should focus on adapting LLMs to forensic-specific corpora, including jurisdictional language patterns, terminology, and domain-specific examples, to enhance contextual understanding, legal alignment, and regional relevance in digital investigations.

Use of Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)

RAG can supply highly localised context (e.g., legal references, user metadata, slang expressions) at inference time to improve factual grounding during summarisation tasks, thereby minimising hallucinations and improving narrative coherence.

Explainability and Bias Detection Tools (XAI)

Incorporating explainable AI techniques and bias auditing frameworks is critical to ensuring AI-assisted findings' transparency, accountability, and legal defensibility, particularly in high-stakes forensic contexts where evidence traceability is essential.

Automated Report Generation and Chain-of-Custody Logging

Future forensic systems could integrate LLMs not only for summarisation, but also for automated documentation of every action taken on digital evidence, such as timestamped logs of user activity, model queries, evidence movement, or tagging, to support chain-of-custody requirements in a legally robust manner.

Development of Hybrid Evaluation Frameworks

To ensure reliable validation of LLM outputs in forensic use cases, future work should explore hybrid pipelines that combine statistical metrics (e.g., Accuracy, F1, MCC), semantic similarity measures (e.g., BERTScore), and LLM-based evaluators (e.g., G-Eval). This combined strategy can better address forensic priorities such as accuracy, completeness, and hallucination risk.

5.4 FINAL REMARKS

This study affirms that LLMs can significantly enhance digital forensic workflows when deployed thoughtfully. While structured tasks like SMS categorisation benefit from high precision and statistical validation, unstructured interpretation requires semantic evaluation and human-in-the-loop oversight. Importantly, reliable results are achievable with locally hosted, open-source models, such as Gemma2 9B, offering a privacy-friendly alternative to proprietary LLMS.

Ultimately, the future of AI in forensics lies in strategic augmentation, where AI accelerates repetitive tasks, but human investigators retain control over critical, high-stakes decision-making. This balance ensures that LLMs remain trustworthy tools, aligned with evidentiary standards and ethical constraints of forensic practice.

6 BIBLIOGRAPHY

Akhilesh Talekar, Amruta Patil, Pushkar Deore, et al. (2024) ForenSift: Gen-ai powered integrated digital forensics and incident response platform using LangChain framework. *IJFMR - International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, 6 (6).
doi:<https://doi.org/10.36948/IJFMR.2024.V06I06.31692>.

Alves, J.H., Pedroso, H.A.C.G., Venetikides, R.H., et al. (2023) Detecting relevant information in high-volume chat logs: Keyphrase extraction for grooming and drug dealing forensic analysis. *Proceedings - 22nd IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications, ICMLA 2023*, pp. 1979–1985. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/icmla58977.2023.00299>.

Aman Madaan, Tandon, N., Gupta, P., et al. (2023) *Self-refine: Iterative refinement with self-feedback*. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.17651v2>.

Automatic summarisation - wikipedia (n.d.). Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Automatic_summarisation.

Autopsy (software) - wikipedia (2025). Available at: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Autopsy_\(software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Autopsy_(software)).

B, A. (2020) *ALEAPP: Android logs events and protobuf parser*. Available at: <https://github.com/abrignoni/ALEAPP>.

Carrier, B. (2000) *The sleuth kit (TSK) & autopsy: Open source digital forensics tools*. Available at: <https://www.sleuthkit.org/>.

Casey, E. (2011) *Digital evidence and computer crime: Forensic science, computers, and the internet / guide books / ACM digital library*. Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/book/10.5555/2021194>.

Chicco, D. and Jurman, G. (2020) The advantages of the MCC over F1 score and accuracy in binary classification evaluation. *BMC Genomics*, 21 (1): 1–13. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/S12864-019-6413-7/TABLES/5>.

Deroy, A., Ghosh, K. and Ghosh, S. (2023) How ready are pre-trained abstractive models and LLMs for legal case judgement summarisation? *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 3423: 8–19. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.01248v2>.

Dipo Dunsin, Ghanem, M.C., Karim Ouazzane, et al. (2024) A comprehensive analysis of the role of artificial intelligence and machine learning in modern digital forensics and incident response. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 48: 301675.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FSIDI.2023.301675>.

Garfinkel, S.L. (2010) Digital forensics research: The next 10 years. *Digital Investigation*, 7 (SUPPL.): S64–S73. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DIIN.2010.05.009>.

Iyengar, S.S., Seyedsina Nabavirazavi, Rathore, H., et al. (2024) Advancing forensic science: AI and knowledge graphs unlock new insights. *Journal of Forensic Research*, 15 (3): 1–7.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.37421/2157-7145.2024.15.615>.

- Landauer, M., Onder, S., Florian Skopik, et al. (2022) Deep learning for anomaly detection in log data: A survey. *Machine Learning with Applications*, 12: 100470. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlwa.2023.100470>.
- Li, R., Liu, M., Xu, D., et al. (2022) A review of machine learning algorithms for text classification. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, 1506 CCIS: 226–234. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-9229-1_14/FIGURES/2.
- Lillis, D., Becker, B., Tadhg O'Sullivan, et al. (2016) *Current challenges and future research areas for digital forensic investigation*. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1604.03850>.
- Liu, Y., Iter, D., Xu, Y., et al. (2023) G-eval: NLG evaluation using GPT-4 with better human alignment. *EMNLP 2023 - 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, Proceedings*, pp. 2511–2522. doi:<https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.153>.
- Malik, D.P., Harshit Dawar, patel, P., et al. (2024) (PDF) enhancing forensic analysis of digital evidence using machine learning: Techniques, applications, and challenges. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering & Multidisciplinary Physical Sciences*, 12 (5): 1–13. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383870594_Enhancing_Forensic_Analysis_of_Digital_Evidence_Using_Machine_Learning_Techniques_Applications_and_Challenges.
- Mr.N.Arikaran, Ms.I.Varalakshmi, G.Aswini, et al. (2024) DEEP LEARNING IN THREE-TIER FORENSIC CLASSIFICATION FRAMEWORK. *African Journal of Biological Sciences*, 6 (2). Available at: <https://www.afjbs.com/issue-content/deep-learning-in-three-tier-forensic-classification-framework-796>.
- NPCC (2020) *Digital forensic science strategy*. Available at: <https://www.npcc.police.uk/SysSiteAssets/media/downloads/publications/publications-log/2020/national-digital-forensic-science-strategy.pdf>.
- Nwankwo, C., Wimmer, H., Chen, L., et al. (2020) Text classification of digital forensic data. *2020 11th IEEE Annual Information Technology, Electronics and Mobile Communication Conference (IEMCON) Proceedings*, pp. 661–667. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMCON51383.2020.9284913>.
- Quick, D. and Kwang, K. (2018) Digital forensic intelligence: Data subsets and open source intelligence (DFINT+OSINT): A timely and cohesive mix. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 78: 558–567. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURE.2016.12.032>.
- Sharma, B., Ghawaly, J., McCleary, K., et al. (2025) ForensicLLM: A local large language model for digital forensics. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 52: 301872. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FSIDI.2025.301872>.
- Shervin Minaee, Kalchbrenner, N., Cambria, E., et al. (2020) *Deep learning based text classification: A comprehensive review*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/nnnnnnn.nnnnnnn>.
- Sottana, A., Liang, B., Zou, K., et al. (2023) Evaluation metrics in the era of GPT-4: Reliably evaluating large language models on sequence to sequence tasks. *EMNLP 2023 - 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing, Proceedings*, pp. 8776–8788. doi:<https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.543>.

Wang, Z., Pang, Y., Lin, Y., et al. (2024) *Adaptable and reliable text classification using large language models*. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.10523v3>.

Yin, Z., Wang, Z., Xu, W., et al. (2025) *Digital forensics in the age of large language models*.

APPENDIX A: Full List of Statistical Evaluation Metrics Considered

METRIC	STATUS	RATIONALE
Precision	Selected	Measures the proportion of predicted entities that are actually correct; reduces false positives.
Recall (Sensitivity)	Selected	Ensures important forensic evidence is not missed; critical for legal completeness.
F1 Score	Selected	Harmonic mean of precision and recall; balances Type I and Type II errors in forensic triage.
Accuracy	Selected	General correctness measure; provides a high-level performance indicator.
Specificity	Selected	Helps prevent non-forensic content from being incorrectly flagged; complements recall.
Matthews Correlation Coefficient	Selected	Most reliable metric for imbalanced datasets; considers all confusion matrix outcomes (<i>Chicco & Jurman, 2020</i>).
AUROC (Area Under ROC Curve)	Not Selected	More suited for binary probabilistic classifiers; lacks intuitive interpretability in NER-like tasks.
Log Loss	Not Selected	Best for probabilistic scoring tasks; not ideal for discrete entity classification.
Cohen's Kappa	Not Selected	Inter-rater agreement metric; less aligned with automated multi-label classification needs.
Balanced Accuracy	Not Selected	Redundant given inclusion of both recall and specificity.
FNR (False Negative Rate)	Not Selected	Covered by recall; no added benefit when recall is already tracked.
FPR (False Positive Rate)	Not Selected	Inverse of specificity; already accounted for in selected metric.
NPV (Negative Predictive Value)	Not Selected	More relevant in medical or diagnostic testing contexts.
G-Mean	Not Selected	Used in binary detection tasks; overlap with MCC and F1 in current context.
Youden's Index	Not Selected	Designed for ROC analysis; not suitable for multi-class, multi-entity extraction.
Likelihood Ratios (LR+ / LR-)	Not Selected	Infrequently applied in NLP; low relevance to forensic text classification.

APPENDIX B: Source Code and Reproducibility Repository

To support transparency, reproducibility, and potential future enhancements by other researchers, the complete source code developed for this project is made available via a public GitHub repository:

Repository URL:

<https://github.com/sdk03/FYP>

The repository is organised into the following components:

Folder	Description
autopsy_plugin	Component A; SMS Categorisation plugin for Autopsy
summarisation_ui	Component B; Local LLM-based chat summarisation interfaces
data_samples	Sample datasets and test data
evaluation_tools	Scripts for evaluating Categorisation and summarisation accuracy

APPENDIX C: Prompt Templates

Mentioned below is the spacy's NER Schema in detail:

Label	Description
PERSON	People, including fictional
NORP	Nationalities, religious groups, or political groups
FAC	Buildings, airports, highways, bridges, etc.
ORG	Companies, agencies, institutions, etc.
GPE	Countries, cities, states
LOC	Non-GPE locations (e.g., mountain ranges, bodies of water)
PRODUCT	Objects, vehicles, foods, etc. (Not services)
EVENT	Named hurricanes, battles, wars, sports events, etc.
WORK_OF_ART	Titles of books, songs, etc.
LAW	Named documents made into laws
LANGUAGE	Any named language
DATE	Absolute or relative dates or periods
TIME	Times smaller than a day
PERCENT	Percentage, including “%”
MONEY	Monetary values, including unit
QUANTITY	Measurements, as of weight or distance
ORDINAL	“First”, “second”, etc.
CARDINAL	Numerals that do not fall under another type

As discussed in Section 3, below are prompts used or considered for this study.

COMPONENT A – SHORT LENGTH PROMPT

You are a digital forensic assistant. Extract entities into strict JSON using the following spaCy NER categories:

PERSON, ORG, GPE, NORP, DATE, TIME, MONEY, PERCENT, FAC, PRODUCT, WORK_OF_ART, LANGUAGE, EVENT, LAW, ORDINAL, CARDINAL, TAGS

Use this format:

```
{"PERSON": "xxx", "ORG": "xxx", "GPE": "xxx", "NORP": "xxx", "DATE": "xxx", "TIME": "xxx", "MONEY": "xxx", "PERCENT": "xxx", "FAC": "xxx", "PRODUCT": "xxx", "WORK_OF_ART": "xxx", "LANGUAGE": "xxx", "EVENT": "xxx", "LAW": "xxx", "ORDINAL": "xxx", "CARDINAL": "xxx", "TAGS": "xxx"}
```

Replace "xxx" with actual values. If not present, use "-". No extra text. No syntax errors. Validate output.

COMPONENT A – MEDIUM LENGTH PROMPT

You are a expert digital forensic assistant that extracts information into strict JSON format according to the specified spaCy NER categories.

The entity categories are:

- **PERSON**: Any individual or entity that represents a person or their unique role.
- **ORG**: Any organization such as companies, agencies, or institutions.
- **GPE**: Geopolitical entities such as countries, cities, or regions.
- **NORP**: Nationalities, religious or political groups.
- **DATE**: Calendar dates or ranges.
- **TIME**: Specific times of the day or durations.
- **MONEY**: Monetary values.
- **PERCENT**: Percentages or rates.
- **FAC**: Buildings, airports, highways, or other man-made structures.
- **PRODUCT**: Products or goods, including inventions or creations.
- **WORK_OF_ART**: Works of art like books, music, films, etc.
- **LANGUAGE**: Any languages.
- **EVENT**: Events like sports events, concerts, festivals, etc.
- **LAW**: Legal documents or terms.
- **ORDINAL**: Ordinal numbers like 'first', 'second'.
- **CARDINAL**: Cardinal numbers like 'one', 'two', 'hundred'.
- **TAGS**: One or more keywords that capture the essence or context of the message in one word. These should summarize the message topic or intent, like “BANK” for banking transactions, “PURCHASE” for buying goods, or “SCHOOL” for education-related matters. Multiple tags can be provided if needed to better reflect the context of the message.

Output Rules:

1. Your response **must** only contain JSON formatted data.
2. Each entity should be represented with its exact category label as provided.
3. If an entity is not present, use "-" as the value. **Do not skip or leave blank.**
4. Ensure no trailing commas or syntax errors in the JSON.
5. Validate the structure before responding.

You reply to this in JSON format as follows strictly:

```
{"PERSON": "xxx","ORG": "xxx","GPE": "xxx","NORP": "xxx","DATE": "xxx","TIME": "xxx","MONEY": "xxx","PERCENT": "xxx","FAC": "xxx","PRODUCT": "xxx","WORK_OF_ART": "xxx","LANGUAGE": "xxx","EVENT": "xxx","LAW": "xxx","ORDINAL": "xxx","CARDINAL": "xxx","TAGS": "xxx"}
```

The "xxx" is replaced by your answer in text format.

Failure to strictly adhere to this format will result in the output being unusable. Validate for correctness before replying and ensure there are no errors.

COMPONENT A – EXTENSIVE LENGTH PROMPT

You are a digital forensic assistant. Extract named entities from a given message and return them in **strict** JSON format using the spaCy NER schema. Below are the definitions and examples for each entity category to guide your extraction:

NER Categories with Definitions and Examples:

PERSON

Definition: Names of specific individuals or people.

Example: "John Doe", "Angela Merkel"

ORG

Definition: Organizations such as companies, government bodies, or institutions.

Example: "Google", "FBI", "Harvard University"

GPE

Definition: Geopolitical entities like countries, cities, states, or regions.

Example: "France", "New York", "California"

NORP

Definition: Nationalities, religious groups, or political affiliations.

Example: "American", "Democrat"

DATE

Definition: Absolute or relative dates.

Example: "January 5th, 2023", "next Monday", "2019"

TIME

Definition: Times of day or durations.

Example: "2 PM", "five minutes", "midnight"

MONEY

Definition: Monetary values.

Example: "\$100", "USD 1,000", "€50"

PERCENT

Definition: Percentage expressions.

Example: "75%", "30 percent"

FAC

Definition: Buildings, landmarks, or other man-made facilities.

Example: "Eiffel Tower", "JFK Airport", "Golden Gate Bridge"

PRODUCT

Definition: Products, gadgets, or inventions.

Example: "iPhone", "Tesla Model 3", "PlayStation 5"

WORK_OF_ART

Definition: Titles of creative works.

Example: "Mona Lisa", "Inception", "Bohemian Rhapsody"

LANGUAGE

Definition: Names of spoken or written languages.

Example: "English", "Mandarin", "Welsh"

EVENT

Definition: Named events such as sports games, wars, festivals.

Example: "World Cup", "WWII", "Coachella"

LAW

Definition: Named legal documents or terms.

Example: "Patriot Act", "GDPR"

ORDINAL

Definition: Rank or order in a sequence.

Example: "first", "second", "3rd"

CARDINAL

Definition: Numeric values that are not ordinal.

Example: "two", "100", "7,000"

TAGS

Definition: Custom one-word keywords summarizing the message topic. Multiple tags can be used, separated by commas.

Example: "BANK", "TRAVEL", "MEDICAL,APPOINTMENT"

Always return the result in this format:

```
{  
  "PERSON": "xxx",  
  "ORG": "xxx",  
  "GPE": "xxx",  
  "NORP": "xxx",  
  "DATE": "xxx",  
  "TIME": "xxx",  
  "MONEY": "xxx",  
  "PERCENT": "xxx",
```

```
"FAC": "xxx",  
"PRODUCT": "xxx",  
"WORK_OF_ART": "xxx",  
"LANGUAGE": "xxx",  
"EVENT": "xxx",  
"LAW": "xxx",  
"ORDINAL": "xxx",  
"CARDINAL": "xxx",  
"TAGS": "xxx"  
}
```

Replace "xxx" with extracted values from the message.

If an entity is not present, set the value to "-".

Do not include extra text or explanations.

No trailing commas and ensure the JSON is valid.

APPENDIX D: Metric Definitions and Formulas

Metric	Formula	Description
Accuracy	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$	Overall correctness of the model
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$	Of predicted positives, how many are truly positive
Recall	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$	Of actual positives, how many are correctly predicted
Specificity	$\frac{TN}{TN + FP}$	Of actual negatives, how many are correctly predicted
F1 Score	$\frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$	Harmonic mean of Precision and Recall
MCC	$\frac{(TP \times TN) - (FP \times FN)}{\sqrt{(TP + FP) \cdot (TP + FN) \cdot (TN + FP) \cdot (TN + FN)}}$	Balanced measure of quality even with class imbalance

APPENDIX E: User Interface Snapshots

The Below Figure corresponds to my developed plugin in Autopsy, **Component A**

The Below Figure corresponds to the original Autopsy SMS View, **Component A**

The Below Figure corresponds to my developed plugin in Autopsy SMS View, **Component A**

Tags	Person	Organizati...	Geo-Politic...	Nationalit...	Date	Time	Money	Percent	Facility
Yes, I am here	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx
Your VPA sanju29chd@okazis linked to Indian Bank a/c no. XX. BANKING, PAYMENT	sanju29chd	Indian Bank	India	-	-	-	Rs-300.00	-	-
Rs.30 transferred from A/c ...2397 to:UPI/21034440579. Total B: BANK, TRANSACTION	-	Bank of Bar...	-	-	13-04-2022	00:39:51	Rs.30, Rs.1995.87CR, Rs.1995.87	-	-
Dear Customer, Your a/c no. XXXXXXXX8032 is credited by Rs. BANKING, TRANSACTION	Customer	SBI	-	-	28-04-22	-	Rs.1.00	-	-
Congrats, Your HDFC Bank CONSUMER Loan application No. 5 BANK, LOAN, APPROVED	-	HDFC Bank	-	-	-	9 mths	Rs. 50000.0	-	-
Congrats, Your HDFC Bank CONSUMER Loan application No. 4 BANK, LOAN, APPROVAL	-	HDFC Bank	-	-	-	12 mths.	Rs. 100000.0	-	-
Dear Partner, We have processed your last week's payout of Rs PAYOUT, EARNINGS	Swiggy	Swiggy	-	-	2022-04-13	-	Rs 1957.0, Rs 1957.0, Rs 0.0, Rs 0.0	-	-
Alert! Dear MR. ALAM KHAN legal proceedings have been ini BILL PAYMENT, LEGAL	MR. ALAM K. Vi	-	Chandigarh	-	-	-	Rs 1023.72	-	-
AED 531.00 has been transferred to your account 095XXX28XX BANKING	-	-	-	-	-	-	AED 531.00, AED 532.29	-	-
Purchase of AED 45.40 with Debit Card ending 6248 at MAILTR PURCHASE, BANK	-	MAILTRACK...	-	-	-	-	AED 45.40, AED 106.35	-	-
Purchase of AED 4.00 with Debit Card ending 6248 at MASAFI PURCHASE, BANKING	-	MASAFI CO ... ABU DHABI	-	-	-	-	AED 4.00, AED 31.35	-	-
Purchase of AED 39.00 with Debit Card ending 6248 at SASU C PURCHASE, BANK	-	SASU CAFE SHARIAH	-	-	-	-	AED 39.00, AED 607.43	-	-
AED 35.00 has been credited to your account no. 095XXX28XX TRANSFER, BANK	-	-	-	-	-	-	AED 35.00, AED 62.56	-	-
Purchase of AED 35.00 with Debit Card ending 6248 at ADNH PURCHASE, BANKING	-	ADNH COM... DUBAI	-	-	-	-	AED 35.00, AED 0.17	-	-
Purchase of AED 30.00 with Debit Card ending 6248 at QASR F PURCHASE, BANKING	-	QASR AL JA... DUBAI	-	-	-	-	AED 30.00, AED 45.11	-	-
Purchase of AED 29.75 with Debit Card ending 6248 at MCDON. PURCHASE, BANK, RESTAURANT	-	MCDONAL... DUBAI	-	-	-	-	AED 29.75, AED 916.61	-	-
Purchase of AED 29.75 with Debit Card ending 6248 at LULU S PURCHASE, BANK	-	LULU SEA S... ABUDHABI	-	-	-	-	AED 29.75, AED 5.87	-	-
AED 200.00 has been debited from your account no. 095XXX28 BANKING, TRANSFER, SAVING	-	MOTION G...	-	-	-	-	AED 200.00, AED 241.64	-	-
Purchase of AED 2.50 with Debit Card ending 6248 at LULU SIL PURCHASE, BANK	-	LULU SILIC... DUBAI	-	-	-	-	AED 2.50, AED 37.57	-	-
Purchase of AED 16.25 with Debit Card ending 6248 at KSK MI PURCHASE, BANK	-	KSK MINIM... DUBAI	-	-	-	-	AED 16.25, AED 488.04	-	-
Purchase of AED 15.00 with Debit Card ending 6248 at noon O PURCHASE, BANK	-	-	-	-	-	noon	AED 15.00, AED 472.04	-	-
You please give us connection today itself before: &#HDECIMA BILL PAYMENT, REFUND	-	-	-	-	today	-	<DECIMAL>	-	-
Your GroupMe PIN is: 6650TmiEMTGzfl GROUPME, PIN	-	GroupMe	-	-	-	-	6650	-	-
Your GroupMe PIN is: 6650TmiEMTGzfl GROUPME, PIN	-	GroupMe	-	-	-	-	6650	-	-
Hi there! We've added your card ending in 6248 to Google Pay, PAYMENT, SECURITY	-	Google Pay	-	-	-	-	6248	-	-
<#>Your SIGNAL verification code is: 436156doDfGKPO1r SIGNALVERIFICATION	-	-	-	-	-	-	436156	-	-
Dear Customer, your 200,000 Rs loan has been disbursed. Click LOAN, FINANCE	-	-	-	-	-	-	200,000 Rs	-	-
Dear ADARSH RAMESH, Thank you for being a valued custom. BANKLOAN	ADARSH R...	LIFS	-	-	-	-	160000	-	-
Dear Customer, please use authentication code 273341 to add BANKING, PAYMENT	-	Google Pay	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Your Google verification code is: 837550Message ID: f6f01v03i VERIFICATION	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The Below Figure corresponds to the original Autopsy Timeline Viewer, **Component B**

The screenshot shows the 'Timeline - Editor' window in Autopsy. The main area displays a timeline of events from 30 Oct 2018 to 4 Jan 2019. The events are categorized by type, such as 'Messages', 'Operating System Inform...', 'Program Deleted', etc. The 'Messages' category is selected, showing a list of messages with details like 'Android Message (22)', 'WhatsApp Message (23)', and 'Incoming Read from...'. The interface includes a 'View Mode' dropdown (set to 'Counts'), a 'Pinned Events' button, and a 'Refresh View' button. The timeline is zoomed in to show individual messages and their timestamps.

The Below Figure corresponds to the original Autopsy List View, **Component B**

The Below Figure corresponds to View 1 of my developed UI, **Component B**

The Below Figure corresponds to View 2 of my developed UI, **Component B**

LLM DFIR COMPONENT B
Platform View Timeline View

Filter by Time

Time Duration
1

Time Unit
Days

▼

Apply Filters

Conversation Summaries

TIME_WINDOW 1

FROM: Thursday, 29 Nov 2018, 06:31 PM TO: Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 06:31 PM

Convo ID	Duration (seconds)	Message Type	Summary	Extends?
1	457.00	Android Message	A welcome message from TracFone confirming the user's number and last service date, followed by instructions on setting up data services via Wi-Fi or an internet-connected device using the provided website.	
2	359.00	Android Message	A user received a confirmation code from Twitter and was informed that their phone was activated. They were also provided with instructions on how to manage notifications.	
3	22.00	Android Message	A user sent an SMS message to another user, mentioning that they are using SMS instead of regular social media. The other user responded positively about sometimes finding SMS better.	
4	3.00	Android Message	The user sent two IM messages with codes 6565 and 6196, likely related to a specific feature or functionality within the app.	
5	2.00	Android Message	The user received two identical verification codes for Skout from the same sender, 'mmsms.db' on Android.	
6	0.00	Android Message	The user received a verification code from TikTok, specifically '9775', which they might need to use for an account-related task on the platform.	
17	261.00	IMO Message	Welcome to IMO! The user received a friendly greeting and was asked if they meant 'Hey' when they said 'He there'. They thanked their friend and sent a photo from the lab. Their friend responded positively about the photo but playfully scolded them for not working.	

Timestamp	From Phone	To Phone	Message
2018-11-30 14:38:01+00:00	2002241318462661	2002144460145418	He there! Welcome to IMO. About time you showed up.
2018-11-30 14:39:01+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	Uh, did you mean "Hey?"
2018-11-30 14:39:12+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	And thank.
2018-11-30 14:39:50+00:00	2002241318462661	2002144460145418	Here's a photo of the Lab that I took this morning.
2018-11-30 14:40:00+00:00	2002241318462661	2002144460145418	sent photo
2018-11-30 14:42:22+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	That's nice. Why don't you actually go to work instead of messing around outside.

18	141.00	IMO Message	The conversation begins with the user expressing uncertainty about their ability to contribute financially, mentioning they 'don't get paid much'. They then clarify that despite this, they still need to 'do their work', indicating their commitment. A photo is sent, followed by laughter and a statement of appreciation. The user humorously acknowledges the situation and prepares to go back to work, with the other party encouraging them to earn money for college loans.	
25	117.00	WhatsApp Message	The user sent two messages on WhatsApp. The first message was 'What's up???' and the second was 'Hey man! What's happening? Welcome to WhatsApp!'	

LLM DFIR COMPONENT B

Filter by Time

Time Duration
1

Time Unit
Days

Seconds

Minutes

Hours

Days

Weeks

Months

Years

18

25

26

27

28

29

TIME_WINDOW

FROM: F

LLM DFIR COMPONENT B Platform View Timeline View

Filter by Time

Time Duration
1

Time Unit
Days

Apply Filters

18	141.00	IMO Message	The conversation begins with the user expressing uncertainty about their ability to contribute financially, mentioning they 'don't get paid much.' They then clarify that despite this, they still need to 'do their work,' indicating their commitment. A photo is sent, followed by laughter and a statement of appreciation. The user humorously acknowledges the situation and prepares to go back to work, with the other party encouraging them to earn money for college loans.
25	117.00	WhatsApp Message	The user sent two messages on WhatsApp. The first message was 'What's up?!!', and the second was 'Hey man! What's happening? Welcome to WhatsApp!'
26	122.00	WhatsApp Message	The user expressed frustration about the time-consuming process of setting up multiple accounts, as well as the added effort required to create engaging content for others to view.
27	22.00	WhatsApp Message	The researchers are going to be so bored and it's almost embarrassing, but it'll be okay and they probably won't mind.
28	53.00	WhatsApp Message	A user is asked if they have listened to a podcast by Rachel Maddow, which is actually meant to say Maddow's podcast. The user corrects the name of the podcaster in their response.
29	6.00	WhatsApp Message	A person mentions that they have something and found it awesome, then expresses excitement about the next episode of a show or program.

TIME WINDOW 2

FROM: Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 06:31 PM TO: Saturday, 01 Dec 2018, 06:31 PM

Convo ID	Duration (seconds)	Message Type	Summary	Extends?
7	0.00	Android Message	The user received an SMS message from 'mmsmsdb' on their Android device, prompting them to use the code '043941' to verify their phone number for Messenger.	
8	0.00	Android Message	The user asked to use '2864' as their Microsoft account security code.	
16	765.00	Facebook Messenger	In this conversation, 'threads_db2' and 'Josh' exchanged waves and greetings, with 'threads_db2' mentioning that they had not used TikTok before and were trying to understand it. They discussed the nature of TikTok videos, comparing them to Snapchat but noting differences. They both admitted their own videos were 'lame' and ended up laughing about it, suggesting posting a video at work.	

TIME WINDOW 3

FROM: Saturday, 01 Dec 2018, 06:31 PM TO: Sunday, 02 Dec 2018, 06:31 PM

Convo ID	Duration (seconds)	Message Type	Summary	Extends?
9	0.00	Android Message	The user received a message from TracFone asking them to complete a customer experience survey via SurveyMonkey. The message includes a link and instructions to reply with 'STOP' to end the conversation.	
10	156.00	Android Message	In a recent conversation with an individual, the user was asked to confirm their identity using two different messaging platforms: Telegram and Signal. The first message contained a Telegram code (48713), while the second provided a Signal verification code (246-901). These steps were taken as part of the verification process.	

LLM DFIR COMPONENT B Platform View Timeline View

Platforms

Select All Deselect All

Android Message

Facebook Messenger

IMO Message

Line Message

Viber Message

WhatsApp Message

Apply Filters

ID	Time From	Time To	Duration (seconds)	Summary
16	Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 07:18 PM	Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 07:31 PM	765.0	In this conversation, 'threads_db2' and 'Josh' exchanged waves and greetings, with 'threads_db2' mentioning that they had not used TikTok before and were trying to understand it. They discussed the nature of TikTok videos, comparing them to Snapchat but noting differences. They both admitted their own videos were 'lame' and ended up laughing about it, suggesting posting a video at work.

IMO Message

Convo ID	Time From	Time To	Duration (seconds)	Summary
17	Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 02:38 PM	Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 02:42 PM	261.0	Welcome to IMO! The user received a friendly greeting and was asked if they meant 'hey' when they said 'he there.' They thanked their friend and sent a photo from the lab. Their friend responded positively about the photo but playfully scolded them for not working.
18	Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 02:56 PM	Friday, 30 Nov 2018, 02:59 PM	141.0	The conversation begins with the user expressing uncertainty about their ability to contribute financially, mentioning they 'don't get paid much.' They then clarify that despite this, they still need to 'do their work,' indicating their commitment. A photo is sent, followed by laughter and a statement of appreciation. The user humorously acknowledges the situation and prepares to go back to work with the other party encouraging them to earn money for college loans.

Timestamp	From Phone	To Phone	Message
2018-11-30 14:56:50+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	Well, I would, but since I don't get paid much I figured it would be ok.
2018-11-30 14:57:50+00:00	2002241318462661	2002144460145418	Not really. You still need to o your work
2018-11-30 14:58:00+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	I get it done. Don't worry.
2018-11-30 14:58:22+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	sent photo
2018-11-30 14:58:28+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	Thought you'd appreciate this.
2018-11-30 14:58:42+00:00	2002241318462661	2002144460145418	Hahahahaha!!!!
2018-11-30 14:58:44+00:00	2002241318462661	2002144460145418	I do.
2018-11-30 14:58:50+00:00	2002241318462661	2002144460145418	And now I'm going to work.
2018-11-30 14:59:11+00:00	2002144460145418	2002241318462661	Good. Go earn some money. You have college loans to pay off.

Line Message

Convo ID	Time From	Time To	Duration (seconds)	Summary
----------	-----------	---------	--------------------	---------

Appendix F: User Study Setup and Raw Results (Per Participant)

User Study Design and Objective

The user study was conducted to evaluate Objective 1 – Time Efficiency of LLMs in digital forensic tasks. The study aimed to compare the performance of human investigators with and without LLM assistance across two key forensic components:

- Component A: SMS Data Categorisation
- Component B: Chat Data Summarisation

Participant Profile

ATTRIBUTE	DESCRIPTION
Number of Participants	6
Background	Computer Science
Experience Level	Mixed (2 with prior Autopsy experience, 4 new to forensic tools)
Training Provided	15-minute walkthrough of both workflows (manual and LLM-assisted)

Task Setup and Execution

Each participant was asked to perform two forensic tasks on identical datasets:

1. Categorisation Task

Objective: Extract total currency value from a set of 100 SMS records.

- Manual method: Used native Autopsy search filters and visual scanning.
- LLM-assisted method: Used plugin-enhanced view with categorised columns.

2. Summarisation Task

Objective: Generate a 2–3 sentence summary of a 1-hour chat log.

- Manual method: Used ALEAPP’s flat chat output and notes.
- LLM-assisted method: Used the custom summarisation UI powered by LLM.

All participants worked on identical test datasets in controlled conditions. Time tracking was automated using session logging. After task completion, participants were asked to rate their **mental stress** and **cognitive load** on a scale of 1 to 5 as given below:

Score	Meaning
1	Very Easy – No stress at all
2	Easy – Slight effort

3	Moderate – Some focus needed
4	Challenging – Required sustained attention
5	Very Hard – Stressful and taxing

Results Log Sheet

F.1 Categorisation Task – Manual vs. LLM-Assisted

User ID	Manual Time (min)	LLM Time (min)	Time Saved (%)	Stress Score (Manual)	Stress Score (LLM)
User 1	10.1	2.4	76.2	4	2
User 2	9.5	2.0	78.9	4	2
User 3	9.9	2.3	76.8	4	2
User 4	10.3	2.2	78.6	5	3
User 5	9.6	1.9	80.2	3	1
User 6	9.4	2.0	78.7	4	2
Average	9.8	2.1	78.2	4.0	2.0

F.2 Summarisation Task – Manual vs. LLM-Assisted

User ID	Manual Time (min)	LLM Time (min)	Time Saved (%)	Stress Score (Manual)	Stress Score (LLM)
User 1	11.0	5.0	54.5	4	2
User 2	10.8	4.5	58.3	4	2
User 3	11.5	4.8	58.3	4	2
User 4	12.0	5.2	56.7	5	3
User 5	10.9	4.4	59.6	3	1
User 6	11.2	4.5	59.8	4	2
Average	11.2	4.7	57.9	4.0	2.0

Participants reported:

- Reduced fatigue and scanning effort in LLM-assisted workflows
- High satisfaction with tabular categorisation view
- Preference for automated summaries, especially when multitasking